

OIKONET A global multidisciplinary network on housing research and learning

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document summarizes the pedagogical activities collaboratively designed and implemented by OIKONET partners from October 2013 to February 2015. Learning spaces are the catalyst around the collaboration takes place. The concept of learning space derives from the pedagogical methodology developed in the previous OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus projects. A learning space is designed by a group of teachers who agrees to carry out shared learning processes about a common theme of study. They also need to agree on the learning outcomes and on the expected skills that students will acquire as a result of participating in the learning space activities, as well as in their evaluation criteria. A learning space is structured in learning activities (e.g. a well-defined stage of the learning process) and tasks (e.g. a specific assignment within a learning activity). Learning activities and tasks constitute the pedagogic framework which can later be implemented in multiple ways by the participating learners. This pedagogic methodology is strongly interwoven with the learning environment OIKODOMOS Workspaces.

The original intention of the OIKONET project was to expand the pedagogic methodology devised in the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus (the pedagogic methods, and tools that support them) to the fifteen schools of architecture and urban planning which are part of the OIKONET network. This change of size in the number of institutions participating in the collaborative design and implementation of learning activities –from eight schools in the OIKODOMOS project to fifteen in OIKONET- has required some strategies to introduce new partners to the philosophy of OIKODOMOS pedagogic methodology, and to the OIKODOMOS Workspaces environment.

As part of the strategy to facilitate the collaboration amongst the members of the OIKONET network, different learning spaces have been developed. The themes for each learning space has been proposed by partners and discussed during the three project meetings which took place in the project. A coordinator has been appointed to each learning space, and all partners had the opportunity to collaborate in the learning design and in the implementation of the activities according to their possibilities. The organization in smaller groups has made collaboration easier. On the other hand, and for assuring the transfer of experience and knowledge gained across the different learning spaces, the results obtained have been discussed in the project meetings. Besides, all partners can have access to any of the on-going learning spaces in OIKODOMOS Workspaces.

This report contains the summary of the work done in five learning spaces:

- **[“Introduction to Housing”](#)** dedicated to introduce first year students to housing, led by School of Architecture of Valencia (Carla Sentieri, coordinator).
- **[“Habitat Regeneration Strategies”](#)**, focusing on the redevelopment of deprived areas at various scales (housing, neighbourhood, city, metropolitan area) encompassing multiple aspects of city life: physical, social, economical and environmental. It is led by the University of Belgrade (Mirjana Devetakovic, coordinator) and by the Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology (Viera Joklova).
- **[“Threshold Matters”](#)** focusing on the study of the intersection of public and domestic spaces. It is led by KU Leuven (Tomas Ooms, coordinator).
- **[“Housing systems”](#)**, dedicated to the study of the concept of housing system, from

design to construction, which has been led the School of Architecture La Salle (Leandro Madrazo, coordinator).

- **“Contemporary living patterns”** dedicated to the preparatory activities to be done by participants in the Lisbon workshop, coordinated by Institut d’Urbanisme de Grenoble (Adriana Diaconu, coordinator).

A summary of the development process and work carried out in each learning space is presented in this report, including the implemented learning activities and tasks, examples of student works, evaluation of the results and reflections about the work done. The learning plan of the learning spaces – except for “Contemporary living patterns”, which was carried out before the learning plan template existed– can be found in the Appendices.

The conclusions that can be derived from the work done in the first half of the project will help to guide the further development of the project.

1.1 Purpose and target group

This document summarizes the collaborative pedagogical activities carried out by the fourteen schools of architecture and urban planning participating in the OIKONET during the first eighteen months of the project. Preparing this document helped partners to structure the work, to assess the results obtained, and to verify the effectiveness of the shared pedagogical methodology. The conclusions derived from the evaluation of the results obtained will inform about the further development of the project.

1.2 Contribution of partners

The School of Architecture La Salle, leader of WP4 Pedagogical Activities, has been coordinating the learning activities summarized in this document. La Salle provided the technological infrastructure to design and implement the learning spaces, using the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus environment. The five learning spaces reported in this document have been carried out with the collaboration of the following partners:

- “Introduction to Housing” led by School of Architecture of Valencia (Carla Sentieri, coordinator), with the collaboration of University of Cyprus (Nadia Charalambous), KU Leuven (Tomas Ooms) and University of Belgrade (Mirjana Devetakovic).
- “Habitat Regeneration Strategies”, led by the University of Belgrade (Mirjana Devetakovic, coordinator), with the participation of Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology (Viera Joklova); Institute d’Urbanisme de Grenoble (Adriana Diaconu), Dublin Institute of Technology (Jim Roche), School of Architecture La Salle (Angel Martin) and Volgograd State University of Architecture and Civil Engineering (Elina Krasilnikova).
- “Threshold Matters”, led by KU Leuven (Tomas Ooms, coordinator) with the participation of Gebze Institute of Technology (Sedef Ozcelik-Guney), Bialystok University of Technology (Adam Jakimowicz), and Dublin Institute of Technology (Jim Roche).
- “Housing Systems”, led by the School of Architecture La Salle (Leandro Madrazo, coordinator), with the participation of the University of Cyprus (Nadia Charalambous).
- “Contemporary living patterns” coordinated by Institut d’Urbanisme de Grenoble (Adriana Diaconu, coordinator), with the participation of all members of the subnetwork Pedagogical Activities.

Altogether, sixteen schools of architecture and urban planning, including two located outside Europe (Universidad de Puerto Rico; Volgograd State University, Russia) have been involved to a greater or lesser extent in these collaborative pedagogic activities.

Besides the schools of architecture and urban planning, the Università della Svizzera italiana has participated carrying out the evaluations of the learning spaces.

1.3 Relations to other activities in the project

The subject-matters addressed in the learning spaces are of interest for the subnetwork Housing Research. During the second half of the project, members of this subnetwork will be involved in the design of the learning activities (e.g. providing readings and references), and commenting and evaluating some of the student works). One of the learning spaces –Civic Housing– has been the result of the collaboration between the School of Architecture La Salle and SostreCivic, a member of the subnetwork Community Participation.

2 DESIGNING AND IMPLEMENTING SHARED LEARNING SPACES

2.1 OIKODOMOS: predecessor of the OIKONET network

The OIKONET project is built upon the previous experience and results obtained with the development and subsequent consolidation of the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus, a project co-financed by the Erasmus Life Learning Program, first in the Erasmus Virtual Campus program (2007-09) and later with the support of the Erasmus Accompanying measures (2010-11). The result of the two combined projects was a pedagogic methodology, based on the principles of constructivism and blended-learning, to design and implement learning activities dedicated to the study of contemporary housing in collaboration. This methodology has been compiled in the [OIKODOMOS Compendium](#) and explained in [on-line tutorials](#).

In the first OIKODOMOS project (2007-09), the participating schools of architecture and urban planning were:

- School of Architecture La Salle, Ramon Llull University, Barcelona, Spain (Coordinator)
- Hogeschool voor Wetenschap & Kunst, Department Architectuur Sint-Lucas, Brussels/Ghent, Belgium (currently integrated in KU Leuven)
- Institut d'Urbanisme IUG, Université Pierre Mendès, Grenoble, France;
- Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology, Bratislava, Slovakia;

Besides, there were two groups specialized in pedagogic design and evaluation:

- KataliSys Limited, Portsmouth, United Kingdom (currently Mr. Paul Riddy, consultant)
- Università della Svizzera Italiana, Lugano, Switzerland.

In the follow-up of the project (2010-11), the Faculty of Architecture, Eastern Mediterranean University, North Cyprus, joined the Consortium. In addition, five schools of architecture participated as associated partners:

- Brandenburg Technical University, Germany
- Gebze Institute of Technology, Turkey
- Escuela Técnica Superior de Arquitectura de Valencia, Spain
- VSUACE, Volgograd State University of Architecture and Civil Engineering, Russia
- ISCTE-University Institute of Lisbon, School of Technology and Architecture, Department of Architecture and Urbanism, Portugal

Eight of the nine schools of architecture and urban planning which participated in the two previous OIKODOMOS projects, as partners or associated partners, are part of the OIKONET consortium now (all except Faculty of Architecture, Eastern Mediterranean University, North Cyprus). These eight institutions, therefore, were familiarized with the pedagogic methodology developed and implemented in OIKODOMOS. Besides, seven new schools have joined the OIKONET project:

- Department of Architecture, Design and Media, Aalborg University, Denmark.
- Faculty of Architecture, University of Belgrade, Serbia.
- Faculty of Architecture, Bialystok University of Technology, Poland
- School of Architecture, Dublin Institute of Technology
- School of Architecture, University of Thessaly, Greece
- Faculty of Architecture, Istanbul Technical University, Turkey
- Universidad de Puerto Rico

2.2 OIKODOMOS pedagogical model

The basic features of the OIKODOMOS pedagogical model are:

- A shared learning space is created by a group of teachers dedicated to a common theme of study
- Within a learning space, learning processes are structured as sequences of learning activities and tasks carried out synchronous and asynchronously by students of the participating schools
- The learning process is carried out in a blended way, carrying out the learning activities and tasks both at the schools and in the on-line learning platforms

Learning activities carried out in the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus are based on a simple conceptual structure (Figure 1). A “Learning space” (named “learning workspace” in the previous OIKODOMOS projects) is the environment created by a group of teachers who decides to develop joint “Learning activities” around a particular theme over a specific period of time. The learning activities are, in turn, made up of “Tasks” which can be either single or grouped in sequences. Sequenced tasks can be constrained to a single “Learning Activity”, or they may cut across different ones. This learning structure is sufficiently flexible and neutral to support different kinds of activities -- from the collaborative development of a project to course assignments - which can be carried out by students working individually or in groups, as well as by schools working independently or in collaboration with others.

Figure 1. Structure of learning activities and tasks

The network of tasks gives rise to a flow of inputs and outputs. In this way, learning can be understood as a process through which some inputs - study themes, assignments, references and readings - give rise to associated outputs (i.e., student works, comments on others' works, peer and teacher evaluations). Thus, the results produced in one task (e.g., an analysis of precedents) can become an input for another task (e.g., a design studio) in another institution. Hence, the timing of the learning activities is not determined exclusively by the courses or academic programs of each university but by the sequencing of the on-site and online activities.

The learning activities have an existence of their own: they become more or less active as more tasks are defined and works are submitted. They move from the virtual to the physical, depending on the sequence of the courses and workshops which are set up; and finally, they come to an end as learners complete their inputs to the learning process.

Figure 2. Structure of learning activities and tasks

The stages in this open-ended learning process might coincide –or not– with an academic program of a participating institution (e.g., semester, quarter). The management of the learning activities executed along this process, collaboratively, with the participation of learners from various institutions, represents a major challenge for teachers. In this context, learning is an open-ended process which can start somewhere for later expanding throughout time and space in an unforeseeable manner. Rather than learning plans, teachers are expected to set up learning strategies and respond to network activity in a timely manner.

2.2.1 Learning design process

The process of creating the network of learning activities starts when a group of teachers agrees on a common theme (the name given to the learning space), which they will develop for a given period of time, typically a semester or an academic year. The teachers then determine the ways in which they will address the theme within their respective courses (seminars or design studios) at their institution. Once the theme has been agreed, different forms of collaboration might be established in order to create a network of shared activities, which can go from punctual collaborations (e.g. an evaluation of the work done at other schools, a video lecture) to joint activities (e.g. carrying out the same project in the design studio).

The activities which are included in a learning space might embrace not only the individual courses at each participating school but also joint workshops where participating students and teachers meet face-to-face during a period of time, typically a week, to carry out specific work on the theme of the learning space. The joint workshop is, therefore, one more learning activity which is linked to the other activities of the learning space. Some of those activities can help to prepare students to the work that will be done in the workshop, and are done, therefore, previously to the workshop. After the workshop, the collaborative activities can

continue on a distant basis in the digital platform as well as in the courses and seminars at each institution. This approach has been successfully implemented in the OIKODOMOS projects, in four workshops in Ghent (2008), Grenoble (2009), Bratislava (2009), Istanbul (2011), and also in the Lisbon workshop carried out in 2014 as part of the OIKONET project (see Deliverable 4.3 International workshops).

2.3 Expanding the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus

A major challenge for the OIKONET project has been to introduce the new partners to the pedagogical methodology developed and implemented in the previous OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus and to the tools associated to it, namely the OIKODOMOS Workspaces, Case Repository and OIKOpedia environments. Besides, it has been necessary to come up with working strategies that enable the collaboration of sixteen schools of architecture and urban planning in the design and implementation of the shared learning activities.

Right from the start of the project, partners received documents that summarize the pedagogic methodology of the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus, and received support to access to the on-line resources available at www.oikodomos.org (compendium, presentations, tutorials) as well as one exemplar of the book “OIKODOMOS Innovating Housing Learning”, which summarizes the work of the previous project.

To introduce new partners to the on-line platform OIKODOMOS Workspaces, during the first months of the project a series of tutorials were given to partners via the Adobe Connect platform. Since then, the developers of the platform, the research group ARC Engineering and Architecture La Salle, have been providing constant support and assistance to the partners who needed so. As part of this strategy of introducing partners to the Workspaces environment, the first learning space –[Civic Housing](#)– was implemented right from the beginning of the project, during the fall semester 2013/14. This learning space was joined by teachers and students of the following partners:

- School of Architecture La Salle (learning space coordinator)
- Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology (students and teachers)
- Institute of Urbanisme Grenoble (teachers)
- Univesità della Svizzera italiana (researcher)
- School of Architecture of Valencia (teachers and students)
- Gebze Institute of Technology (teachers and students)
- Faculty of Architecture, University of Belgrade (teacher)
- Universidad Politécnica de Puerto Rico (teachers and students)
- School of Architecture, KU Leuven (teachers and students)
- University Institute of Lisbon (teacher)

The teachers who joined the learning space could follow the work being done by the other groups providing students as well.

2.4 Implementing new learning spaces

Following the first meeting of the subnetwork Pedagogical Activities held in Barcelona on January 29, 2014, different themes to create learning spaces for the OIKONET project were discussed and then implemented in the following months. It was decided to create three learning spaces:

- [“Introduction to Housing”](#) dedicated to introduce first year students to housing, led by School of Architecture of Valencia (Carla Sentieri, coordinator).
- [“Contemporary living patterns”](#) dedicated to the preparatory activities to be done by participants in the Lisbon workshop, coordinated by Institut d’Urbanisme de Grenoble (Adriana Diaconu, coordinator).
- [“Threshold Matters”](#) focusing on the study of the intersection of public and domestic spaces, which is led by KU Leuven (Tomas Ooms, coordinator).

The three learning spaces started to be developed immediately after the meeting, and a first version of the learning structure and objectives were completed in the spring semester 2013/14. Two of them –“Introduction to Housing”, “Threshold Matters” – were partially implemented as well, while “Contemporary living patterns” was implemented in the two months prior to the Lisbon Workshop (May/June 2014).

A fourth learning space, with the name [“Habitat Regeneration Strategies”](#), was proposed during the second meeting of the subnetwork in Lisbon, July 2014. The topic was proposed by the University of Belgrade, which was conducting some pedagogical activities on this issue.

The fifth learning space, [“Housing systems”](#), has been proposed by the School of Architecture La Salle, being linked to the OIKONET elective course carried out in the fall semester.

During the second meeting of the subnetwork in Lisbon, it was decided to improve the process of designing the learning spaces. With this purpose, a template would be used to describe the learning plan of the learning space, before this would come into place. This learning plan includes the theme, objectives, participants and their roles, learning activities and tasks, and the expected learning outcomes, among other. The learning plans of the learning spaces – except “Contemporary living patterns”, which was already completed– can be found in the Appendices.

The following chapters in this report describe the work carried out in these four learning spaces. The reported work focuses on the consolidated phase of the development of the learning spaces, once the learning structure and the participating partners were established. The comparison between the results reported and the original plan laid out in the templates helps to identify the value of the outcomes as well as the difficulties found in the implementation.

3 INTRODUCTION TO HOUSING

3.1 Introduction

During the first meeting of the subnetwork Pedagogical Activities held in January 2014 in Barcelona, it was agreed to create a learning space dedicated to address such concerns through the collaborative design and implementation of sequences of learning activities that introduce students to the basic principles of the design of a house. These learning activities attempt to overcome boundaries between physical and digital learning spaces by promoting a blended learning approach across institutions. Three schools agreed to participate in the design of the pedagogic structure of the learning space “[Introduction to housing](#)” (IH): School of Architecture, Valencia (ETSA-UPV) (task leader); University of Cyprus (UCY) and Faculty of Architecture of Belgrade University (AF Belgrade). The three schools have been collaborating in the activities from January until now (February 2015).

The activities and tasks which are part of this learning space have been jointly designed by teachers of the Faculty of Architecture of Belgrade, Serbia; the Department of Architecture at the University of Cyprus and the Architecture School of the Universitat Politècnica de Valencia, Spain. This collaboration has enabled the participating teachers to exchange contents of their academic programs and to share their experiences about teaching introductory courses at their respective institutions.

The first challenge faced in the design of this learning space was to agree on a common plan of collaborative teaching on this specific topic which reflects the pedagogic objectives of the participating institutions (see Appendix A). During the first semester of collaboration, the aim of the participating institutions was to put together their respective curricula in one single learning program. This proved infeasible considering the available time. Therefore, from January 2014 until June 2014 the School of Architecture of Valencia proceeded to transpose the program of their introductory course onto the learning structure of activities and tasks which the OIKODOMOS Workspaces structure provides. The other two schools incorporated the proposed activities and tasks into their programs and introduced new ones into the Workspaces in collaboration with the School of Architecture of Valencia

During the second year the collaboration between the participating institutions was reconsidered.

From September to December 2014, the objective was to establish relationships between students and between students and teachers through comments on students works uploaded to Workspaces. Students from UCY and Valencia participated in one of the tasks and uploaded their work to the workspace. Students from UCY commented on the work.

Finally, during the spring semester, at the moment of writing this report, a revised form of collaboration is taking place, which builds on a common plan of collaborative teaching on this specific topic which reflects to a great extent the pedagogic objectives of the participating institutions. The partners that are participating are UCY and ETSA-UPV. The Learning Activities, Learning Tasks, and schedule have been jointly designed. Students from both schools upload their work which is both used as a reference/resource for students from both institutions and is commented on by both students and teachers. Virtual lectures from tutors at distinct phases have also been planned.

3.2 Topic

The house is undoubtedly one of the most important vehicles of exploring the social and experiential dimensions of architecture. An understanding of the ways in which the house as a spatial form, relates to the social, the cultural, the individual in the context of the increasingly divided, complex and differentiated experiences of contemporary life, is an important concern for architecture educators across the globe.

The purpose of this learning space is to introduce first year students to some of the fundamental principles of architecture -through both analysis and synthesis-. Students learn the basic design tools (measuring a building, drawing plans and sections, describing the building subsystems such as the structure and façade elements) by representing a building at scale 1:100. The experience that the students acquired through this work on representation and analysis of an architectural work is then applied to make a basic design of a single family residence.

Consequently, Learning Activities included precedents analysis, understanding of the concepts of home and house, context analysis and analysis of users' profiles. Learning Tasks included demonstration of knowledge of the relevant theoretical background, demonstration of coherence and continuity in the development of the design process, appropriate use of different representation techniques (verbally, textual and graphic-digital and analogue) in order to communicate the ideas (concepts and design proposals) in an effective manner, ability to demonstrate team working skills through their contribution to each project and ability to critique their own work and that of others by reference to established models of good practice and the appropriate standards.

3.3 Implemented learning activities

The activities that were carried out during the spring semester of 2013/14, from those described in the original plan described in Appendix A, have been the following:

- **LA53 RECOGNIZING SPACE.** Architects create spaces. Therefore, it makes sense that the first step in an introduction to architecture is to learn, to perceive and to represent space. The purpose of this activity is to learn to recognize the places we inhabit.

- TK 1 What is a house?

The goal of this task is to distinguish the concepts of house and home: what makes a house important for us and why. Students are expected to address issues such as: what makes you feel good at a home? These reflections are summarized in a A3 document combining different materials and techniques (texts, drawings, photographs).

Figure 3. Submission of Task 1 by student Miquel Lloret, School of Architecture Valencia

During spring semester 2013-14 this task has been implemented by ETSA_UPV. Students could comment the outcomes of this task. For instance, some students from KUL wrote comments during the task: “Getting to Know the platform” from the learning space “Threshold Matters”.

This is an example of comment by Jana Vervaeet from University of KU Leuven:

Hi Melania,

Is it possible to give a short description about your collage?

Your lay-out is clean and sober. The text are short and clear but I think they need a bit more explanation. However I like that you marked the key words. I think you made a writing error: ‘aN space’. You don’t speak about the places where you feel good in a house, although it is asked in the assignment. I would like to read them. You speak about principles of all time but you use three pictures of contemporary houses. Now it looks like they’re just applied in our modern houses. For example the connection with the outside goes way back, but it was different then. Maybe you could show us other examples of houses that make your presentation more complete? Do you agree with me?

Kind regards,

Jana

There was no answer because the student was from the year 2013-14 and the comment was done during the course 2014-15. This is one thing we have to improve, the continuity after a course is finalized.

During the fall semester 2014-15, this task has been implemented by ETSA_UPV. The outcomes of this task were commented by teachers from other schools and by students from University of Cyprus. They formulated questions to students, to make them continue thinking about the issues they have identified.

This is an example of comment by teacher Tomas Ooms from KU Leaven to Nieves Bonmati:

Hi

First of all, nice that you use sketches and combine that with text. This work very well in the presentation. You approach the house from a viewpoint of functionality making reference to adaptability etc. But what I think is an important element that you touch upon is the personalisation or appropriation of space: the use can decide how he uses the space. I think this is an essential quality of architecture. The same counts for the relation between the inside and the outside, the permeability.

The question that you didn't answer is: where do you feel good in the house. Maybe this is the question of when a house becomes a home... Have you considered this? I guess that the concept of appropriation and permeability are essential in this.

There were some answers like this one from Nieves Bonmati to Tomas Ooms:

Hi Tomas,

Thank you for your comment.

For us the most comfortable space in the house is the bedroom, because is the place where people can look for themself. It is their own world, where they can make changes and feel good. We thought on this question but we didn't reflect it well.

This is an example of comment by student Maria Theodoulou from University of Cyprus:

Hi,

I have to say that i like your point of view, it is true that the building it is nothing without the people so home ise a combination of activities that people do, their needs and their feelings. So a house have to be able to embody these by changing and transforming the inside and the outside of it!

- LA55 LEARNING ACTIVITY 3: PRECEDENT ANALYSIS. The purpose of this activity is to learn from precedents, to identify solutions provided from previous projects and to transform them into new ones.

TK11 Analysis of residential architecture. Analysis of international examples of residential architecture (context, users, social, economic, environmental variables).

The screenshot shows a workspace titled 'INTRODUCTION TO HOUSING' with a user 'Sentieri, Carla' logged in. The main task is 'LA65 TK11 analysis of residential architecture-single houses' by Charalambous, Nadia, a team task from 23 January 2015 to 30 March 2015. Below the task, there are filters for Description, Predecessor Task, Successor Task, Keywords, Learning Outcomes, Resources, and Groups. The main content area shows 'Deliverables of UCY_APH201_2015 (9)' ordered by date. It displays a grid of student submissions, each with a thumbnail image, author name, date, and a 'Ga' (Gallery) checkbox. The submissions include: Giannakopoulos, Kyrkos + 2 (06/03/2015), Poliviou, Pavlos + 2 (06/03/2015), Komodromou, Paraskevi + 2 (01/03/2015), Giannakopoulos, Kyrkos + 2 (01/03/2015), Klidara, Inni + 2 (01/03/2015), Andreou, Christina + 1 (01/03/2015), and Panayi (01/03/2015). The 'Ga' checkbox is checked for the submission by Giannakopoulos, Kyrkos + 2. At the bottom, there is a 'Comments on group' section.

Figure 4. Submission of Task 11 by students of UCY from University of Cyprus

During spring semester 2014-15, this task has been implemented by students from the University of Cyprus. The outcomes of this task were commented by teachers from other schools and by students from University of ETSA_UPV. They formulated questions to students, to make them continue thinking about the issues they have identified.

Example of comment by teacher Carla Sentieri from ETSA_UPV (Valencia):

Hi all of you,

I think you can be interested in this two project:

-House in Buñola _Francisco Cifuentes because the use of the material is very interesting

<http://tectonicablog.com/?p=25607>

-Kingo House _Utzon because is the same organization but different scale.

<http://www.e-architect.co.uk/denmark/kingo-houses>

I recommend you to look for books with more information.

Good work!

And comment by student María Reyes:

Tur, Maria Reyes on [06/03/2015]:

Hello , I found a page explaining this project and I think it will be interesting to you.

<http://www.moma.org/interactives/exhibitions/1999/un-privatehouse>

- **LA58 USER PROFILE ANALYSIS.** Houses are a complex expression of the social and individual worlds of their occupants, in which social structure, the patterns and conventions of everyday life seem to be closely related to the idiosyncratic and many times chaotic circumstances of people's everyday lives. Students are encouraged to understand that the design of a "home" needs to address the practicalities of everyday living while responding at the same time to the owner's idiosyncrasy, personality and dreams. It is therefore important to be able to analyse, understand and address possible users' profile.

- TK12 Analysis of potential users

Students are randomly given existing user profiles and are asked to analyze them (daily routines, hobbies, personalities, spatial patterns) . Results are presented through the use of photos and diagrams.

Figure 5. Submission of Task 12 by student Celia Castillo, School of Architecture Valencia

During spring semester 2014-15. This task has been done by ETSA_UPV. The outcomes of this task were commented by teacher from Valencia. The revision by the teacher of this exercise/task has been done on line, on the platform, giving references from other learning spaces.

This is an example of comment by teacher Carla Sentieri from ETSA_UPV (Valencia):

Hi Sandra,

I recommend you to look the exercise presented in Workspaces: Housing Systems (TK7) of Doyle Deirdre. There is an example that can be useful for you.

- **LA 59 CONTEXT ANALYSIS.** The objective of this L.A. is to introduce the analysis of the context, reflect differences between ethnic, cultural and social categories, including gender divisions between men and women or generational differences between adults and children. Many times homes may reflect differences in environmental conditions (climate, light, air, topography). The way these differences are found in the house may vary in

different cultures and different geographic areas and may be observed in the way domestic space is designed and organized. Students are encouraged to understand through this activity the ways in which domestic space is site/context specific.

- **TK13 Visual mapping of context.** Students are asked to respond to specific sites - contexts given by their tutors employing visual ethnography methods. They are asked to represent context specific characteristics (cultural, social, environmental) through both digital and printed photo essays.

Figure 6. Submission of Task 13 by student Marta López, School of Architecture Valencia

During spring semester 2014-15. This task has been done by ETSA_UPV and UCY. The outcomes of this task were commented by teachers and students from these schools.

This is an example of comments made to a work of Celia Castillo from ETSA_UPV (Valencia):

(Carla Sentieri) Hi Celia,

The information is good, but there is a lot of information. For the next work try to separate the different themes and it will be easier to read it.

Good work!

(Andreas Panayiotou) Hola Celia,

Indeed you have good information, but in my opinion it should be easier to understand without reading. For example you could have better memorandums, so you make your map more easy to read without having passages. It is better to show more processed images and sketches rather than a good text. :)

(Celia Castillo)

Thanks for all your words, they are so useful. Next time I'll try to write less and draw more. Doing this, information will be clearer and more attractive!

- **LA 60 AT HOME. NEW DESIGN PROPOSALS.** Taking into consideration all the work produced through the preceding tasks students are asked to design a "home" in a specific context that addresses local conditions and culture, the practicalities of everyday living and the users' profile, personality and dreams. Understanding the context bound relationship between the spatial structure of domestic space and the social life of the inhabitants is one of the central challenges of this studio. We are interested in the ways in which the home as a spatial form, relates to the social, the cultural, the individual in the context of the increasingly divided, complex and differentiated experiences of contemporary life.

- **TK 14 House design proposals. Initial concepts.** Students are asked to develop initial ideas of new domestic spaces for a given context and user profile.

This task is in process this spring semester 2014-15 and there are some results but there are no comments yet.

Figure 7. Submission of Task 14 by student Angela Mañas, School of Architecture Valencia

- **TK117 Collective housing project.** The student are asked to develop new design proposals of collective housing in their particular context and users profile.

This task is in process this spring semester 2014-15 and there are no results yet

3.4 Blended-learning environment

The activities have been carried out in the classroom as well as in the on-line learning environments.

3.4.1 On-site activities

The elective course is different for the schools. In ETSA-UPV there have been two groups participating on the platform. During the spring semester 2013-14 (January-June) the students of the first year design studio participate. These students meet twice a week for 1,5 hours each time. The activities and tasks undertaken in the learning space are part of the students' assignments in the studio.

During the spring semester of 2013-14 and fall and spring semesters of 2014-15 the students of second year design studio participate. These students meet twice a week for 3 hours each time. The activities and tasks undertaken in the learning space are also part of the students' assignments in the studio.

In UCY there have also been two different groups participating in the learning space. During the spring semesters (January-June) the students of the second year design studio participate. These students meet twice a week for 6 hours each time. The activities and tasks undertaken in the learning space are part of the students' assignments in the studio.

During the fall semester (September-December) both second and fourth year students participate through elective courses. These students meet once a week for three hours and share some of the tasks implemented in Workspaces.

The time in class is dedicated to introduce the theoretical basis of the exercises, to make presentations of students works, to discuss the comments received through the OIKODOMOS Workspaces environment, and to actually implement the tasks.

3.4.2. On-line activities

OIKODOMOS Workspaces was used to structure the learning activities and to organize the collaborations in between partners. Both the comments and the shared tasks were submitted on this environment.

3.5 Collaborative activities

From the School of Architecture Valencia, 72 students participating from the undergraduate program and 1 tutor, from the School of Cyprus, 60 students and 1 tutor participated in the activities (around 30 students each semester for each group). They carried out the tasks described in Section 3.3.

As described in the beginning of the document, we can speak about three processes that conform to the following periods: spring semester of 2013-14, autumn-winter semester of 2014-15 and 2014-15 spring semester. In the first semester, when the learning space was initiated, the Valencia school was the one who led the work and used the OIKODOMOS Workspaces platform throughout the school semester.

During the spring semester 2013-14, a common learning structure was developed.

During the fall semester 2014-15 the participating institutions shared a common task. Students from ETSA-UPV and UCY uploaded the deliverables of the shared task. Based on this, there were two kinds of collaborative activities:

- Comments by Tomas Ooms, teacher from KUL
- Comments by students from UCY

During the current semester, spring 2014-15, learning activities and tasks have been collaboratively designed in alignment with the common pedagogic goals which are reflected in the learning outcomes set by the participating institutions (see Appendix A). The tasks that

are going to be performed are the following:

-TK11 Analysis of residential architecture-single house. Reflecting on this topic, the students from UCY uploaded exercises and students from ETSA_UPV and Carla Sentieri, professor at the School of Architecture in Valencia commented several submissions on this task, and proposed new references.

-TK12 Analysis of potential users. Reflecting on this topic, the students from ETSA_UPV uploaded works and and Carla Sentieri, professor at the School of Architecture in Valencia commented several submissions on this task, proposing new references. The students from UCY will upload in the next weeks..

-TK13 Visual mapping of context. Reflecting on this topic, the students from UCY and students from ETSA_UPV uploaded exercises and Carla Sentieri, professor at the School of Architecture in Valencia and the students from the different schools commented several submissions on this task.

During this semester, 24 students from the ETSA-UPV and 30 from UCY are participating on the learning space activities.

The ideal situation is that deliverables were submitted by students from both schools at the same time so that they can keep track of work from students from other schools and discuss the it, thus obtaining supplementary information that contributes to develop their own work.

Another way of asynchronous cooperation can be established if the teacher of each school knows at what point the work of the other school will be uploaded and, this way, to enable her to include them in the learning process.

3.6 Outcomes

Four university partners have actively joined the learning activities on the topic of “Introduction to Housing” until now, involving 4 teachers and 162 students.

Altogether 261 students’ submissions and 22 teachers have been active in the IH learning space. Students’ submissions distributed by learning partners are as follow: AF Belgrade (41 submissions); ETSA-UPV Valencia (179 submissions); UCY (41 submissions).

Students’ submissions distributed by specific learning activities are as follows: LA53 – Recognize the space (114 submissions); LA54 – Interpretation of a text (30 submissions); LA55 – Precedent analysis (42 submissions); LA58 – User Profile Analysis (31 submissions); LA 59 – Context Analysis (18 submissions); LA60 – At Home_ New design proposals (26 submissions)

Some learning resources facilitated to students can be useful for future editions of the learning space. They are available in the RESOURCES area of the OIKODOMOS Workspaces

(http://www.oikodomos.org/workspaces/index.php/activities/viewwork/activity_id:55)

3.7 Evaluation of results

The first application of IH collaborative learning activities from January 2014 till March 2015 gaver rise to both positive and negative observations. During this period three different forms of collaborative activities took place. It is important to differentiate them to be able to build on the positive aspects and to address the negative ones.

During the spring semester 2013-14, three schools (UCY, Belgrade and ETSA-UPV) arrived to a define a common learning structure. This was the most important goal. After one

semester where each school participated as much as it was possible, two schools continued collaborating collaboration, UCY and ETSA-UPV. As a result of this collaboration, the first learning structure was redesigned and a timetable to carry out the activities in the academic year 2014-15 was agreed.

The evaluation of the learning Space “Introduction to housing” was conducted through an on-line questionnaire that was submitted to the students of the Universidad Politécnica de Valencia (UPV) at the end of the semester spring 2013-14. There is no evaluation yet evaluation of the activities taking place this year.

The main objective of the evaluation was to assess the effectiveness of learning activities and achievement of learning outcomes, and the level of integration of the on-line platform into the students’ learning experience.

The first questions regarded students’ expectations: beyond topic-related expectations (learn the basics to realize an architectural project, learn about handling measures and materials, analyse spaces and houses, learn about new forms of houses), students had strong expectations regarding networking and sharing: they expected to virtually meet people from other countries and exchange ideas, methodologies and projects with them. In general, these expectations have been somewhat met: for 7 students they were fully met, for 9 students they were somewhat met, for 9 students only partially met.

When asked about what they had learned during the course, students mentioned topic-related knowledge and skills, communication and presentation skills and attitudinal skills (e.g. importance of precision and details, importance of hand drawing and creativity). Furthermore, 10 students claimed that the participation in the learning space had changed or refined their approach to planning or design.

In general, the use of the on-line platform was not considered very important for the course during this period because it was in an early phase of implementation.

Participating in the joint learning space was considered as particularly useful for getting in contact and communicating with others, and for sharing projects.

In general, students thought that participating in the learning space was positive and interesting. What they liked most were networking and collaboration on activities: sharing and comparing works, learning from others, meeting other students and architects (18 students mentioned this issue).

A majority of students found the international learning experience motivating, encouraging and inspiring. It was interesting for them to know what others think about their work. From their comments in the evaluation questionnaire students expressed: “it has been a great experience..., ...hope this system will spread among other subjects too..., ...very good project..., ...trying to support international collaboration between universities”. At the same time, however, they expressed: “...only few comments from foreign students received..., ...we did not collaborate, there was no time for closer contact..., ...very time consuming method..., ...no feedback on given comments, no real exchange of opinions..”

The learning space gave students the opportunity to be exposed to the work of fellow students but also to present their work to both students and colleagues of the participating schools. It also gave tutors the opportunity to work in collaboration, to get to know diverse teaching methods as well as the work done by students from other schools. However, the first implementation of the learning space proved that more time and better planning was required in order to get all its potential.

A persistent problem seems is the difficulty to reconcile partners’ regular learning activities

at their institutions with the collaborative learning activities carried out in the learning space. Differences in schedules, learning and tasks approaches resulted in difficulties with harmonization of collaborative activities.

3.8 Conclusions and further steps

The teaching activities discussed in this report concern the first implementation of the learning space “Introduction to Housing”. The pedagogic structure created within this learning space has been the base for the enhancements and developments taken place in the on-going implementation.

Both students and tutors found the participation in the learning space to be fruitful. The tutors involved had the opportunity to apply blended learning in their teaching, to get feedback from colleagues in different academic environments and to get familiar with different and diverse teaching methods and learning resources. Participating students were exposed to different cultural and academic contexts, they were able to experience different methods of learning through the virtual campus and they had the opportunity to comment on other students’ work and to receive feedback from both peers and tutors.

Participating teachers noted the potential of developing blended learning environments using OIKODOMOS Workspaces, as a way to facilitate interaction between students from various institutions and to contribute to a better understanding of the multiplicity and complexity of housing issues. Learning activities and tasks could be collaboratively designed in alignment with the common pedagogic goals which are reflected in the learning outcomes set by the participating institutions. Teachers from the participating institutions could continue developing collaboratively designed learning activities and tasks, describing at the same time the learning outcomes to be used to jointly assess students’ work. Careful planning of tasks that can be accommodated to the needs of each institution’s schedule would enable to use the tasks previously executed by other institutions as references for their work. This will also enable a more effective peer evaluation at each distinct phase of the learning process. Further interaction between participating institutions needs to be promoted through virtual lectures and discussions.

4 HABITAT REGENERATION STRATEGIES

4.1 Introduction

The creation of the learning space “Habitat Regeneration Strategies” (HRS) was firstly discussed during the second meeting of subnetwork Pedagogic Activities, which took place in Lisbon in July 2014. AF Belgrade had recently carried out a participatory learning activity “Integrative Urban Design in Urban Regeneration of Savamala”, during a summer workshop which concludes with an exhibition at AF Belgrade in June 2014. Relevant stakeholders in the area object of study participated in the activities. Their involvement followed an incremental and cyclical process of learning, each phase widening the level of participation among stakeholders and partners: from reflection towards collaboration. Students’ designs were presented via videoconference to other OIKONET partners – La Salle and FASTU.

Based on that experience, this learning space is aimed at supporting a wide range of learning activities in concerning the regeneration of cities, in Europe and worldwide, with a particular focus on the issues of liveability, housing and resilience. Urban or housing regeneration processes involve relatively large number of OIKONET partners from the different subnetworks. The research subnetwork is preparing a reader on housing regeneration processes. The community participation subnetwork is dealing with the involvement of residents in participatory processes to create sustainable communities. In this context, this learning space can be use as catalyst that bring together the three subnetworks, Housing Research and Community Participation, with Pedagogical Activities.

The objective of the learning space HRS is to explore in theoretical and practical ways the complex issue of housing regeneration. Learning activities are aimed at analysing particular cases, identifying problems and needs for regeneration, exploring the examples of housing regeneration strategies, forging new visions and proposing actions which bring together multiple domains (urban planning, architecture, urban geography).

The initiators of the HRS learning space are: Faculty of Architecture at Belgrade University (AF Belgrade) – (coordinator), Faculty of Architecture STU in Bratislava (FASTU), Institute de Urbanisme UPMF Grenoble (IUG) and Faculty of Architecture VSUACE Volgograd (VSUACE). Later on another OIKONET partners joined the learning space HRS: La Salle Barcelona (La Salle), Dublin Institute of Technology (DIT) and UTH University of Thessaly (UTH). UN Habitat is providing support with their published studies and recorded presentations.

4.2 Topic

Many towns have wasted, un-used or under-used land, brownfields. Developing urban regeneration strategies are an opportunity for to activate those areas and to improve the living environment. According to Eurocities, urban regeneration is at the core of city planning. Urban regeneration can be defined as the integrated local redevelopment of deprived areas (housing, neighbourhood, city, metropolitan area). It covers many aspects of city life: physical, social, economical and environmental. A regeneration process integrates the multiple dimensions of an urban design process with the local governance and stakeholders.

The creation of an OIKONET learning space on housing regeneration offers an opportunity to study this complex issue from in an international and multidisciplinary context that facilitates sharing experiences and analysing examples on urban regeneration worldwide.

The activities carried out in the learning space, foster the collaboration of students, teachers and researchers at the international level.

4.3 Implemented learning activities

- **LA 69 WORKSPACE INTRODUCTION.** Based on previous experiences in using virtual environments, AF Belgrade firstly introduced this learning activity aimed at socialization of participating students.

- **TK4 Welcome / introduce yourself.** Student introduced themselves explaining their interest in the topics of housing regeneration. Students from FASTU and AF-Belgrade did this task.

- **TK5 Group introduction.** Identify members of the group, establish a communication international fellow students (e-mail, Skype, FB group, G+...), make a short common introduction of the group. This task was done by students from FASTU.

Hi! I would like to introduce to you our group. My name is Veronika Gramerová and I am working with my classmate Ivana Naďová. We are students of architecture at The Slovak University of Technology and we will work together on a project called habitat regeneration strategies. The goal of this design studio is to design a regeneration project of a part of Bratislava called Petržalka.

Figure 8. Submission of Task 4 by students Veronika Gramerová and Ivana Naďová, FASTU

- **LA70 Urban Habitat Regeneration and Integrative Urban Design in Sustainable Development** The next learning activity aimed at introducing the problem of habitat regeneration in general, to explain the role and activities of UN Habitat and their educational resources, to define sustainability and analyse a successful case of habitat regeneration.

- **TK 6 Exploring the case of Ciutat Vella.** Within this task, the case of regeneration of Ciutat Vella has been selected for analysis by four groups of Belgrade students, by different aspects: social, institutional, economic and ecological. Three of the four submissions are present in the Workspaces.

Figure 9. Submission of Task 6 by students Ostojić, Milan; Vuković, Iva Teodora; Mihić, Tamara; Zečević, Nina, AF

- **TK8 Exploring the examples of urban regeneration strategies.** In this task, students working in groups were required to search and identify good examples in regeneration strategies in waterfront and brownfield habitat central zones in the cities all over the world and explain, why they selected these examples, having in mind possible application in their respected case studies. Three partners joined this task: AF Belgrade (with 3 submissions), FASTU Bratislava (with 48 submissions) and VSUACE Volgograd (with 2 submissions). Students frequently browsed their peers' works and commented them. This international students' research together with the resource documents uploaded by teachers represents significant information base on the examples of housing regeneration strategies worldwide.

Figure 10. Submission of Task 8 by student Nadya Abdrashitova, VSUACE

- **TK18 Present appropriate precedent of urban habitat regeneration.** It was created by DIT in February 2015 for Dublin students joining the HRS learning space to identify an appropriate precedent of urban habitat. Four individual submissions were presented.

- **LA71 CREATING HABITAT REGENERATION STRATEGIES.** The next learning activity focused on a local or selected international problem and at analysing regeneration strategies behind the examined case studies. It aimed at analysing particular cases of habitat, identifying problems and needs for regeneration, main and the most important stakeholders, identifying or creating wider regeneration visions and proposing set of related actions from the specific disciplinary viewpoint.

- **TK9 Habitat analyses.** This task dealt with the analyses of particular cases of habitat, with wider relationships, traffic, functional analysis, analysis of greenery, identification of problems and needs for regeneration, identifying or creating wider regeneration visions and proposing set of related actions from the specific disciplinary viewpoint (urban planning, architecture, urban geography...).

Figure 11. Submission of Task 9 by group of Miriam Szabová, FASTU

Comments

Wei, Si on [15/11/2014]: Good day to you.

We are students of Institut of Urbanism of Grenoble in France who are working on the subject of Bratislava morphology. We read your document and we found it's extremely interesting. At the same time, we have a question for you: "Do you think it is important to have the system of Bratislava's tramway on the map of connectivity analysis"?. (Because we are the group who study influence of transport structure's influence on form of city.) Do you consider it as a factor important in the structure of the city? best regards, friends of Grenoble.

Figure 12. Submission of Task 9 by group of Miriam Szabová, FASTU

Hi,

I think, the tramway is in our city very important. It is very good to have different options for transport - I can see it everyday how tram is important, when mornings are traffic jams in the streets and it is impossible to be in time by bus or car. In our city are the tram also used in the pedestrian zone for transport.

I hope, I answered a bit your question, but I am not sure, if I understood it right. BR. Miriam

- TK10 Urban morphology and regeneration of riverbanks of four European case studies: Belgrade, Bordeaux, Bratislava and Nantes. This task was proposed by IUG. The main aim was to analyse cities where regeneration strategies of waterfront areas are important issues. It considered the historical and geographical reasons that influenced first the creation, than the spontaneous and planned evolution of these cities. First phase of the task comprised three exercises in which students analysed the formation and evolution of selected city. They should understand the reasons for the creation of the chosen city and the characteristics of its original/natural site; the importance and role of the city at local, regional and international level throughout history, as well as the layout of the historical core and of the original road connections need to be identified at this point. Next exercises were based on the understanding the growth patterns of the chosen city and identifying the relationships of railways and waterways to urban forms. Finally students analysed the urban projects concerning the regeneration of riverside areas in the chosen city, from the last thirty years. They synthesised the main tendencies, principles and guiding design ideas for the regeneration of brownfields, of docks, for the transformation of infrastructure and of public space, for the (re)creation of habitat etc.

The urban development of Nantes

From the XVIIIth century to the XIXth century, the île de Nantes was occupied by lots of shipyards but it was not part of Nantes' urbanization. During the XXth century, the shipyard activity is gradually abandoned until the closing down of the shipyards which has turned the île de Nantes into an unused space.

Figure 13. Submission of Task 10 by group of Chevalier, Esther, IUG

- TK11 Sustainable mobility. This task focused on the case of the Bratislava Petržalka central axis is strongly determined by the planned bearing transport system represented by ground tram system, connecting Petržalka with old city and its amenities. Planning new tram line and stands generates the creation of new public spaces in dwelling surroundings. Student's research was aimed on the sustainable mobility principles, which will be discussed on the workshop with experts and citizens in planned participative action.

Figure 14. Submission of Task 11 by group of Katarina Ružeková, FASTU

- **TK15 Process of visioning.** This task was most important for students from AF-Belgrade. After being introduced with the methodology of integrative visioning, students divided in four groups defined possible visions for the regeneration of Krupanj.

Figure 15. Two examples of integrative visioning for Krupanj, AF

- **TK17 What is sustainability and resilience.** This task was performed by AF-Belgrade students, who explored and presented the concept of resilience in relation to

sustainability.

-TK 16 Conceptual Model Design. This task was most relevant for FASTU students. Based on the analyses and examples of regeneration strategies tasks, students in this task presented their conceptual design for particular case study regeneration strategy. Part of final presentations of FASTU students have been transferred online via Adobe Connect videoconference to partners for critique, discussions and commenting. Participated partners: La Salle Barcelona, IUG Grenoble, AF Belgrade and VSUACE Volgograd.

Figure 16. Submission of Task 16 by group of Juraj Fabrici, FASTU

- LA72 HABITAT REGENERATION ACTION. The last learning activity specified in HRS Workspaces was LA 72- Habitat Regeneration Action - aimed at synthesis of the research done on regeneration approaches and strategies, as well as on the analyses of particular case studies, with the finalization in the proposal of the regeneration action.

- TK19 Present appropriate precedent of urban habitat regeneration. DIT students identified a precedent of urban habitat regeneration and presented them graphically and in text explaining how it relates to the stated criteria of HRS learning space.

Figure 17. Submission of Task 19 by student Shelly-Ann O'Dea, DIT

- **TK20 Presentation of the action/design.** AF Belgrade students (with 2 submissions) presented their final decisions, both group work and individual actions/designs according to the vision presented in one of the previous tasks and learning activities.

4.4 Blended-learning environment

Collaborative on-line and off-line learning activities started in September 2014 by the definition of learning activities and initial tasks and by the involvement of subjects available for the collaborative learning process.

Oikodomos Workspaces environment “Habitat Regeneration Strategies”

(<http://www.oikodomos.org/workspaces/index.php/workshops/preview/24>) has been used for structured learning activities, including:

- Common learning tasks for student submissions;
- Sharing, reviewing and commenting student submissions;
- Using provided learning materials (lectures, texts, links, examples, including two recorded video-lectures).

A Facebook Group: “OIKONET Habitat Regeneration Strategies” was created after the Lisbon Workshop, with the aim to facilitate and make more transparent communication among the participants in the Workspaces creation and maintenance.

(<https://www.facebook.com/groups/716510478414701/>) The group is also used for spreading information about cooperation and activities in the Workspaces to a wider local and regional academic audience (the colleagues from Serbia, Albania, Hungary and Macedonia were invited to follow the activities).

Other academic systems for group-mails and informations are utilized as well. All these digital tools supported the blended collaborative learning activities of participating partners

4.5 Collaborative activities

Figure 18. Collaborative learning activities in HRS Workspaces environment (09/2014 – 01/2015)

AF Belgrade involved 2 teachers: Tatjana Mrdjenovic, Mirjana Devetakovic and 17 actively working students. The teaching activity at AF Belgrade, supported by HRS learning space, was an elective titled: OIKONET Habitat Regeneration Strategies. It was focused on the flood disaster regeneration strategies in the town of Krupanj (Serbia). The most important point in the stage was site visit, talking with representatives of the municipality of Krupanj and with citizens affected by recent catastrophic floods in the region. For dissemination of information from the site visit, the students preferred to use Facebook Group and did so in some cases directly from the site. This visit was a base for discussion of possible strategies of regeneration.

FASTU Bratislava integrated learning activities of OIKONET HRS to regular learning activities at the Faculty during winter term 2014/15 in obligatory subject Specialized CAD Design Studio (4th year Architecture and Urbanism). Involved were 3 teachers: Viera Joklova, Juraj Furdík, Ivor Mečiar and approx. 90 students. Most of the teaching was in English. The aim of the course was to analyse the case study, the identification of problems, research on the housing regeneration issues and development of regeneration strategies visions for the area, which was set in the Petržalka Central development axis, around the water corridor of Croatian creek. This case study was solved by the VSUACE students and teachers as well. Viera Joklova gave the online lecture “Bratislava development strategies”, recorded in the task resources and thus available for other partners.

IUG Grenoble integrated learning activities of OIKONET HRS to regular learning activities at the Institute during winter term 2014/15 in the subject Urban morphology (2nd year Geography, specialization in Town Planning). They solved the task on Urban morphology and regeneration of riverbanks of four European case studies: Belgrade, Bordeaux, Bratislava and Nantes. This task allows understanding of contemporary urban design and planning solutions in relation to the specific geographical and historical context of each riverside city under scrutiny. The deliverables further offer participants in the Workspaces the

possibility to identify and reflect on common patterns and specificities among European cities and their planning and design strategies for regeneration. Involved were 1 teacher: Adriana Diaconu and approx. 31 students. Students' final designs were presented on poster exhibition at IUG.

VSUACE Volgograd involved 2 teachers: Elina Krasilnikova and Larisa Kuzina and 5 actively working students in the bachelor design studio on Landscape Design. They solved the Bratislava Petržalka regeneration strategies in collaboration with FASTU students and teachers. Elina Krasilnikova gave the online lecture „The development strategy of Dublin. Urban development and regeneration of the urban district North Fringe in Dublin“, recorded to task resources and available for other partners.

La Salle Barcelona involved 2 teachers: Leandro Madrazo and Angel Martin Cojo for final videoconference presentations of FASTU students.

DIT Dublin joined the HRS learning space in February 2015. In the regeneration strategies course coherent with the aims of OIKONET learning space is involved 1 teacher: Jim Roche and approx. 19 students.

UTH Thessaly is planning to involve 1 teacher: Vaso Trova and 40 students of second year Urban Design Studio on “Eco-Urbanism”. The course focuses on the development of an infill site adjacent to a railway station in the city of Larissa.

4.6 Outcomes

Six university partners have actively joined the learning activities on the topic of Habitat (Housing) Regeneration Strategies until now, involving 11 teachers and 162 students for collaborative activities on the issue. Learning space supported the multidisciplinary approaches in the process of housing regeneration, so as the portfolio of participating partners is the spectrum of architecture, urbanism, strategic planning and geography.

Altogether 255 students' submissions and 44 teachers' resources documents were uploaded to Workspaces HRS. Students' submissions distributed by learning partners are as follow: AF Belgrade (36 submissions, additional 13 submissions are at Facebook Group HRS); FASTU Bratislava (181 submissions); IUG Grenoble (10 submissions), VSUACE Volgograd (16 submissions); DIT Dublin (12 submissions).

Students' submissions distributed by specific learning activities are as follow: LA69 – The Workspace Intro (43 submissions); LA70 – Urban Habitat Regeneration and Integrative Urban Design in Sustainable Development (60 submissions); LA71 - Creating Habitat Regeneration Strategies (142 submissions); LA72 - Habitat Regeneration Action (10 submissions).

Five videoconferencing learning sessions were realized, some of them were recorded to Resources documentation:

- Lecture by Elina Krasilnikova, VSUACE: “Dublin regeneration strategies”, (<http://enginyeria.adobeconnect.com/p2vkbqkzvmp/>); partners AF Belgrade and FASTU participated online.
- Lecture by Viera Joklova, FASTU: “Bratislava development strategies”, (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KrsJBAexPaA>); partners AF Belgrade and VSUACE participated online.
- Videoconference session between FASTU and VSUACE, responding the questions of VSUACE students on the case study analyses.

- Videoconference session of the final presentations of FASTU students; online participated La Salle, IUG, AF, VSUACE.
- Videoconference session describing the Workspaces HRS and realized activities, realized between AF and DIT.

4.7 Evaluation of results

The first application of HRS collaborative learning activities from September 2014 till January 2015 brought both positive and negative observations.

A lot of students found the international learning experience motivating, encouraging and inspiring, it was interesting for them to know, what others like about their work. From their comments in the evaluation questionnaire students expressed: "...it has been a great experience..., ...hope this system will spread among other subjects too..., ...very good project..., ...trying to support international collaboration between universities." At the same time, however, they expressed: "...only few comments from foreign students received..., ...we did not collaborate, there was no time for closer contact..., ...very time consuming method..., ...no feedback on given comments, no real exchange of opinions..."

Persistent problem seems to be with the reconciliation of partners' regular learning activities with the collaborative learning activities of OIKONET HRS. Learning process is usually affected by a number of variables inputs and learning partners during this process gained first experiences with the scope and learning/teaching approaches of their distant partners. Differences in schedules, learning and tasks approaches resulted in troubles with harmonization of collaborative activities. Learning activities and tasks were not properly planned before the start, they have been created during the teaching and reflected the actual needs and possibilities of participating partner. There seems to be too much tasks, some of them are very similar and could be joined; some tasks are without appropriate specification.

Partners experienced short time for designing and implementing the learning space; the original planning did not work as expected. Partners contributed in different ways, without necessarily sharing an overall view of the learning space (participating in final review, providing learning resources, commenting student's works).

Use of English was a problem. Some partners had students who could not use English; they uploaded works in other languages, this was not useful for collaboration. English should be imperative, deliverables in other languages are without learning value for other partners. As the conclusion, a requirement to post in OIKONET Workspaces in English, should be explicitly highlighted in the marking procedure.

4.8 Conclusions and further steps

The topic of housing regeneration is attracting new partners, so the continuation of collaborative activities in this learning space will continue taking place in the coming semesters. AF Belgrade will continue with the theme in a summer semester studio named "Resilient city and housing". VSUACE Volgograd will join with master students on urban design studio on urban regeneration of Bratislava Petržalka. IUG Grenoble, FASTU Bratislava and La Salle Barcelona will join with teacher's comments to students' work. DIT Dublin and UTH Thessaly will join as newly incoming to the learning structure of HRS with their learning activities. Proposed is the organization of summer school on the HRS topic at FASTU.

Reference documents uploaded in Workspaces can be used further for collaborative learning activities. The members of the subnetwork Housing Research could help to increase the

knowledge base adding new resources related to urban regeneration and public participation. Researchers could also help to define the tasks, so they can become co-designers of the learning processes. Also, this learning space can facilitate the creation of ties with the subnetwork Community Participation.

The topic of housing regeneration strategies will be the theme of the second OIKONET international conference, which will be held at FASTU Bratislava on 24-25 September 2015 (<http://oikonet-conference-bratislava.blogspot.com.es/>).

5 THRESHOLD MATTERS

5.1 Introduction

The “Threshold Matters” (TM) learning space was created in the spring semester of 2013/14, as a joint initiative of the Faculty of Architecture KU Leuven, Belgium, and Gebze Technical University, Turkey. Soon after the Dublin Institute of Technology (DIT), Ireland, and Bialystok University of Technology (BUT), Poland, joined the learning space.

This first implementation of the learning activities planned took place already in the spring semester of 2013/14, and a second has taken place in the fall semester of the 2014/2015. KU Leuven, GTU and School of Architecture of Valencia, (ETSA-UPV), Spain, participated in this second edition. As we are writing this report, DIT is integrating some of the “Threshold Matters” activities in their spring semester design course (see also 5.8 Conclusions and further steps).

The meetings held during the meetings of the subnetwork Pedagogical Activities in Lisbon in July 2014 represented a turning point in the development of the “Threshold Matters” learning space. During the meetings there was time to reflect on the experience of the first edition of the learning space and to assess its relevance for the OIKONET project (i.e. Learning design, Integration of shared learning activities in the academic programs, Blended learning). Besides, there was the opportunity to learn from the experience of the other workspaces that were reported during the meetings. One of the relevant outcomes of the meeting was the learning design template that should be used to describe a learning space before it starts to be implemented. The learning plan and objectives can be found in Appendix B.

5.2 Topic

“The threshold provides the key to the transition and connection between two areas with divergent territorial claims and, as a place in its own right, it constitutes essentially, the spatial condition for the meeting and dialogue between areas of different orders.” (Herman Hertzberger)

Threshold is an ambiguous zone often described in planning terms as ‘public/private’ or ‘private/public’, a zone in housing that affords options for socialising and amenity, a place to meet neighbours and for children to play. That zone in architecture between the public and private domains is often ambiguous, having many layers and meanings with associated varied treatments across different cultures and climates. The boundaries that legally define property for example do not define visual privacy. In housing, threshold represents a series of transitions between the very public realm of the street and the very private world of the dwelling.

Acknowledging that the issue needs to be understood from multifarious perspectives - sociological, theoretical, spatial / sectional ideas to construction systems and textural / material treatments - a range of learning activities and tasks were developed for students.

5.3 Implemented learning activities

This report primarily focuses on the fall and spring semesters of the 2014/2015 academic year. During and immediately after the Lisbon meetings, a programme was established using the Learning Design Template. The Learning Activities and Tasks were agreed jointly by GTU, KUL, DIT and ESTA-V under the coordination of KUL and GTU.

The following learning activities and tasks have been implemented:

- LA56 Exploration of concepts

- TK1 Visual Impulses
- TK6 Getting to Know the Platform
- TK7 #Threshold Matters
- TK8 Thresholds in parallel
- TK9 Architectural Review
- TK4 Getting to Know the Platform alt. Take
- TK15 Architectural Review alt. Take

- LA57 Urban CT Scanning / Urban Tomography

- TK10 Urban Tomography
- TK11 Urban CT Scanning written to graphical

- LA 73 A Micro perspective: the “case study”

- TK12 Design assignment: A Moment Between U & I
- TK13 A Lonely Mans’s Shelter
- TK17 A cut-away sectional axonometric exploring threshold treatments in students’ designs

LA56 “Exploration of Concepts” focused on discovering and ‘uploading’ pre-defined concepts relating to Thresholds. This particular learning activity sought to explore a number of concepts with respect to the architectural expression of the philosophical background of the different concepts. The keywords for this learning activities were: Knowledge Mining; Thresholds; Spatial and Social Patterns; Interfaces.

The second LA was called LA57 “Urban CT Scanning / Urban Tomography”. It is the revolving point of the sequence of LA’s and TK’s.

This particular Learning Activity sought to investigate, through Urban Tomography of the urban realm within housing settlements (and/or detail studies of threshold spaces on particular project sites), the architectural expression of the concepts that were explored in the LA Exploration upon Concepts. Urban Tomography is a term for imageing by sections or sectioning.

Keywords for the LA “Urban CT Scanning / Urban Tomography” were: Mapping; Boundaries; Thresholds; Urban Analysis, Section.

The third LA entitled “A Micro perspective: the case study” concluded the Threshold Matters Learning space. The goal was to somehow challenge prevailing perceptions of how to relate projects to the public domain. Inspired by the research undertaken in the previous LA’s, the students were required, through the use of sections, to develop a design that exemplified their new understanding of “Threshold Matters”. Keywords for this LA were: Design, Spatial reflection.

What follows is the description of the processes involved to carry out the above tasks, the collaboration between the partners and the kind of outcomes and interactions between the students themselves and between the students and the teachers

- LA56 EXPLORATION OF CONCEPTS

- **TK1 Visual Impulses.** The activities started for GTU students with TK1 Visual Impulses. This task was completed by GTU students as part of their design studio. The results were uploaded in the OIKODOMOS Workspaces platform and ETSA-UPV made comments on the work.

- TK6 Getting to Know the OIKODOMOS platform

This TM learning space for KU Leuven started with TK06 Getting to know the platform. KU Leuven and GTU students explored various outputs in different OIKODOMOS Workspaces and commented on them. The comments were prepared by students and reviewed by the teacher before being posted to the workspace. The goal was to get to know the ICT platform on which they would need to work and to learn how to formulate a constructive comment.

- TK7 #Threshold Matters

KUL students selected four of the concepts explored in the description of LA56 Explorations upon concepts of “Threshold Matters” and briefly researched them, condensing each one into a 140-character description through which they showed their understanding and interpretation of that concept. The messages were posted on the workspace and some were selected and communicated on the TM twitter account.

The output was discussed by GTU students and then commented on using a maximum of 25 words.

A comparative analysis between the discussions in the GTU Studio and how KUL Students cover the issues will follow.

ETSA-UPV students read the descriptions and looked for a new text (from the theories of architecture) to complement it. They did so through making a constructive comment

Figure 19. Extract of the final Update 3.0 (a report produced by the student reporter) of Tasks 1, 6 and 7 by student Nele Santy containing the work of Mustafa Özdemir

- TK8 Thresholds in parallel

A series of design workshops was organised in order to orientate the second year architecture students of GTU to consider the challenge of relating form and function on a given site. The GTU students were asked to consider one particular space in Uskudar and in particular the notions of: the ground, the wall and the canopy. The work was done through making models and supported by sketches. In a joint Skype meeting KUL students reflected on the uploaded work.

- TK9 Architectural Review

This task built on the relation between the topic of the learning space and the existing OIKODOMOS Case Repository (a product from the preceding OIKODOMOS project). The students selected an architectural project that relates to the topics they discussed in the #Threshold Matters. As a result, a graphic review was proposed on how the selected project related to the #Threshold Matters concepts.

ETSA-UPV students looked for another project that relates to the same topic and gave that as reference to the KU Leuven students. In their turn, KU Leuven students reacted to those proposals leading to a short conversation (ref. Joachims Affordance).

Figure 20. Extract of the final Update 3.0 (a report produced by the student reporter) of Task 9 by student Nele Santy and containing the work of Joachim Bekkers on the left. On the right some of the comments posted by students from ETSA-UPV

- TK14 Getting to know the platform - alt.take

DIT students firstly attended an online introductory seminar on Urban Tomography delivered by Tomas Ooms of KUL. They were then asked to log on to the OIKODOMOS Workspaces, upload their photos and explore the tasks and the work already done in the fall semester of 2014/2015 by students from KUL and GTU. Each student was required to make a short comment or ask questions on two of the projects. In addition teacher Jim Roche of DIT commented on some of the work done by KUL and GTU students.

The intention here was to encourage the DIT students to begin considering the issue of threshold in its multivarious layers and meanings and to learn through reflection and collaboration.

Example of comment by Walsh, Ailbhe from DIT to this study by Kwinten Delvaux from KUL (final output of TK12) A moment between U and I):

Hi, your project is very interesting. The series of layered thresholds you set out appear to create nice intimate spaces which your axonometric drawing visualises proficiently. It could be interesting to further explore the proportions of the thresholds in the way you have already done with the frames.

FRAMING THE THRESHOLD Threshold as spatial condition

House
Street
Threshold spaces
Private
Heavyness
Public
Lightness

01

THRESHOLD MATTERS
Design exercise: KUL, 2014

Does a building works when the hierarchy of spaces are working well together?
#TK7-Oikonet

The design is a link between the street and a private house or an apartment block. The intention was to extend the experience of transition. The spatial conditions of the threshold are framed and extended which will be more stimulating for the senses than just a cut through a wall. A series of architectural spaces are constructed that transition into another space. Inspiration found by M.C. Escher, *Metamorphosis*.

Design steps: (0) (1) (02)
1. 5 frames are made, starting from thin glass panel becoming a thin frame and ending up with a blank wall, interacting with each other both visually as fysicaly. Creating spaces more intimate or private.
2. Changes of directions are important thresholds to go to the different rooms (see axonometric): from the street (1) to the threshold spaces(2) to the house/apartments (3).

references:
Metamorphosis II (see also *Metamorphosis I*)
more info: www.oikonet.org

Tk12 - Learning activity 37
OIKONET elective 2014
Faculty of Architecture - KU Leuven
www.oikonet.org - www.twitter.com/ThresholdMatters
Deborah Kwintan

Figure 21. XXXXX

- TK15 Architectural Review - alt. take: Review of an existing threshold

DIT students were then asked to study an appropriate precedent of threshold in housing and present it graphically on one A3 sheet to include at least one photo, one sketch, a maximum 100-word commentary explaining how it relates to the stated criteria of this learning space. They then had to respond briefly to any comments made by collaborating students / teachers from other institutes.

THRESHOLD MATTERS | PRECEDENT STUDY | MARK REDMOND | D10119873

A BOY HANDING A WOMAN A BASKET IN A DOORWAY | PIETER DE HOOCH | 1663

In this 17th century painting by Pieter De Hooch of a boy in a doorway handing a woman a basket you can clearly see a deep and deliberate threshold that is in everyday existence. Van Hooch paints a series of Thresholds, from the chair in the corner to the mat to the step down into an outside space, step up into the shadows across to a street then across a canal to the neighbour staring back at you.

SECTION THROUGH SPACE

Figure 22. Submission of Task 15 by student Mark Redmond

In this 17th century painting by Pieter De Hooch of a boy in a doorway handing a woman a basket you can clearly see a deep and deliberate threshold that is in everyday existence. Van Hooch paints a series of Thresholds, from the chair in the corner to the mat to the step down into an outside space, step up into the shadows across to a street then across a canal to the neighbour staring back at you.

- LA57 URBAN CT SCANNING / URBAN TOMOGRAPHY.

- TK10 Urban CT Scanning / Urban Tomography

Students from the Faculty of Architecture KU Leuven explored and researched the possibilities of Urban Tomography. The concept of Urban Tomography was introduced through a lecture. The lecture was made available as a resource on the workspace and repeated over Skype at GTU and ESTA-V. Within this task the students produced a series of sections on a selected urban site that highlight the issue of threshold on an urban level. As the students explored the opportunities of Urban Tomography they also selected sites. Thus the possibility to link to their Master Dissertation emerged.

Students from GTU studied the Urban Tomographies from KUL and formulated questions. GTU had to perform Urban Tomographies on their own site and they could learn from the work done by the KUL students. The questions were posted on the TM FB group and discussed during a joint Skype meeting in which all KUL students, GTU students and a teacher from La Salle participated.

Figure 23. Extract of the final Update 3.0 (a report produced by the student reporter) of Task 10 by student Nele Santy and containing the work of Clàudia Carracas & Maciej Sidorowicz (left) and comment by Angel Martin (La Salle teacher)

This Skype session served as a kind of review. This session was also used to generate feedback on the GTU results of TK 08 Threshold in Parallel.

As noted above the lecture on Urban Tomography was held for ESTA-V students on November 11 and on November 14 at GTU. The results from the Urban Tomography explorations showed that they are useful mechanisms for developing knowledge and understanding about a site. A possibility worth exploring in a future learning space could be to start using them as a design tool.

LaSalle formulated comments on the uploaded Tomographies as did the GTU students. This LA overall proved to be extremely successful and will very likely lead to a further related one.

Figure 24. Screenshot of the Threshold Matters Facebook group showing the Skype online –review in progress and indicating the number of people reached: 71

- TK11 Urban CT Scanning written to graphical

A series of sections was produced by GTU students in the Urban Tomography manner regarding the concepts that were tackled by KUL students in TK7. A3 posters were designed for the case study area of Uskudar/Istanbul (linking to the result of TK8).

- LA73 A Micro perspective: case study

- TK12 Design assignment: A Moment Between U & I

Through this assignment students were obliged to question our contemporary way of relating projects to the public domain. Primarily through the use of sections and guided by their research interest developed in the previous tasks, they designed a space that exemplified their understanding of “Threshold Matters”. The final output is a model and a 3D section. For this they could work on a specific existing site or in a more theoretical abstract context

Figure 25. Screenshot of the Threshold Matters Facebook page showing the first version of the models produced for Task 12. It shows also the number of people reached: 69

The process was followed during the OIKONET elective seminars and the final designs were uploaded in the workspace.

Students from Valencia (ESTA-V) were asked to reflect on their own studio design assignment from the perspective of the UT and design results of the KUL students. ESTA-V had to select one of the spaces of their design project that related to one of the research topics (concepts) they explored by following the KUL students work track.

(The students from Valencia have been working on an existing building from the 1960's called Virgen del Carmen.) They uploaded their reflections in TK 12.

Figure 26. Final output of Task 12 A Moment Between U&I, work of Clàudia Carreras

- TK13 A Lonely Mans's Shelter

The students were required to design a "Lonely man's shelter" that aspires to utilise thresholds as a means for the user to interact with the everyday public life of Uskudar. An A2 poster containing the design proposals and conceptual approaches was uploaded on the workspace.

- TK17 An axonometrical reading of thresholds in housing

At time of writing this report DIT students were required to complete a cut-away sectional axonometric of one of the key threshold spaces in their timber housing scheme identifying the textural treatment of surfaces and to present this graphically on one A3 sheet to include a maximum 150-word description and 2 or 3 other key drawings of their scheme showing their attitude to threshold. A pdf of this A3 study is to be uploaded to the workspace. Students are also required to respond to any comments made by collaborating students / teachers from other institutes.

Concluding the learning space

KUL students had a final meeting on 13 February 2015. The meeting took place in the offices of CONIXRDBM architects in Brussels (BE) and its a purpose was to close the OIKONET elective course with a final reflection on the latest outputs. A report of this meeting was produced and uploaded in the bulletin board of the workspace. There were 12 students present. In addition to the discussion on the WS the students visited the offices of the architectural firm that was hosting the meeting. With that meeting the first full run of the TM learning space was concluded. The final review of the DIT students' work occurred on Tuesday 14 April with Tomas Ooms as guest critic

5.4 Blended-learning environment

The activities have been carried out in the classroom as well as in the on-line learning environments.

5.4.1 On-site activities

The “Threshold Matters” learning space was active in different institutions and in different environments. A short description on how it was imbedded in the curricula is given in ‘Collaborative activities’.

5.4.2 On-line activities

OIKODOMOS Workspaces was used to structure the learning activities and to organize the collaborations in between different partners. Both the comments and the shared tasks were submitted on OIKODOMOS Workspaces.

The OIKODOMOS Case Repository was used in TK9 Architectural Review to create collections that illustrate different Concepts of Threshold. The results of this task were also submitted on OIKODOMOS Workspaces to be shared and commented by teachers and students from other institutions.

A TWITTER account was created linked to TK7 # Threshold Matters:

<https://twitter.com/ThresholdMatter>. Through this account the one-liners produced by students in the context of TK7 were broadcasted.

Figure 27. Screenshot from the Threshold Matters Twitter account

A Facebook group “Threshold Matters” was created as a communication platform complementing the OIKODOMOS Workspaces. The posts ranged from sharing of questions and information to updates on the on-going work, reminders for approaching deadlines and posting of final results.

Figure 28. Screenshot from the Threshold Matters Facebook group. The group has 75 members and contains 100+ entries

Skype was used between the teachers to have regular updates and coordination meetings, to deliver lectures and to host one online live review

5.5 Collaborative activities

Students with different profiles participated in the “Threshold Matters” learning space. The KUL master students, since they were the most advanced in their learning, took the lead and were generally the first to work on most of the tasks. In this way they could inspire the other students participating in the learning space. The GTU second year bachelor students, learned from and followed the approach of the KUL students. The ESTA-V Master students followed the process and progress of the learning activities.

At the Faculty of Architecture of the KU Leuven the OIKONET activities are embedded as an OIKONET elective course. Our previous experiences with the OIKODOMOS pedagogic model showed us that a coherent and full integration of the OIKONET pedagogic activities in the curriculum is a necessity to ensure success. As it is an elective course, Master students from Architecture and Interior Architecture can inscribe. In total 15 students selected the course thus filling the course completely. It is organised as a design seminar based on interaction and collaboration in the context of the OIKONET project. The elective is linked to the international workshop and to the international OIKONET conference. The course grants 5 ECTS credits. The course is designed as a stand-alone course but during the implementation of one of the tasks (TK10 Urban Tomography) the opportunity to inform the Masters dissertation of the participants emerged.

At ESTA-UPV the learning space was linked to the “Recycling of public space and urban design” course, which is part of the “Architecture and sustainable habitat” Master (MAAPUD) leading to 7 ECTS.

The students worked in groups and the assessment of the group work comprised 85% of the

final individual rating. The remaining 15% is related to the outcome and participation in the OIKONET platform. Participation in the learning space has mostly been established during class time.

At GTU, within the design studio teaching agenda, the concept of “dwelling” is tackled in the fall semester for the second year undergraduate students every year. For the formulation of the single house design, functioning of a dwelling with respect to the user and urban interventions regarding the integration of the house with the urban setting; the GTU design studio applied a “folded design teaching” method. That method was crucial since the learning process continued both in the design studio as an “hands on” action as well as an virtual common learning space shared on the OIKONET platform via OIKODOMOS Workspaces

At DIT the TM learning space was introduced to 18 fourth year architecture students as a series of tasks related to their current housing project in Waterford city. Following a Skype lecture from Tomas Ooms of KU Leuven, the students embraced the issue of threshold by initially making comments on work done by the KU Leuven students in the first semester. They then studied a relevant threshold precedent and uploaded it to the TM learning space with a short commentary and answered any comments left by other students or teachers. At time of writing they are preparing a 3-d exploratory drawn study of a threshold space in their housing scheme to be uploaded with commentary to the TM learning space. Overall the combined tasks of the TM learning space represent 8% of the total grade for their housing project.

5.6 Outcomes

For KUL 15 students uploaded 104 deliverables in 5 tasks and made numerous contributions in other tasks, other learning spaces, and social media.

GTU integrated 44 students that uploaded 15 deliverables in 4 tasks and made contributions in other tasks, in other learning spaces, and in the social media. Because of heavy snowfall in Istanbul the timing to perform the planned activities was disturbed. Towards the middle of the activities the number of participating GTU students was reduced to the 3 students that were selected to participate in the COTTBUS workshop.

ESTA-V collaborated with 13 students uploading 9 deliverables in one task and made numerous contributions in other tasks.

La Salle participated with one teacher in the Skype review and in commenting on TK8 and TK10.

In DIT, 18 students participated in 3 tasks and one Skype lecture. The participation is still ongoing.

Some learning resources facilitated to students can be useful for future editions of the learning space. They are available in the RESOURCES area of the OIKODOMOS Workspaces and/or on the Facebook Threshold Matters group.

- Bibliography related to Threshold Matters:
- Building a Theatre that Remakes Itself, Joshua Prince-Ramus, TED talk Oct 2009;
- The Production of Space, Henri Lefebvre;
- Experience and Use of the Dwelling, PERLA SERFATY-GARZON;
- Lessons for Students in Architecture, Hermann Hertzberger, 1991.

- Hermann Hertzberger, 1959-86, Buildings and Projects, 1987.
- Urban Tomography, Lecture by Tomas Ooms;
- Skype review between GTU, KUL and LaSalle (see TK10 Urban Tomography)

5.7 Evaluation of results

One of the focus points of the OIKONET project is the opening up of what is going on within a learning space to a broader audience. As a first step and experiment a reporter (or media manager) was appointed. This student was exempt from the tasks but was present at all OIKONET seminars and followed the online activities. In her role the reporter managed the twitter account and the Facebook group. During the semester two issues were released. These are a kind of newsletter reduced to one A4 enabling a short and fast reading. For the reporting at the WP4 meeting in Istanbul a full visual overview of the activities of the “Threshold Matters” learning space was delivered.

Figure 29. Issues 1.0 and 2.0 produced by the student reporter and distributed through the social media and e-mail

From experience we knew that email is useful in co-ordinating and collaborating only to a limited extent. Therefore most emails that were exchanged between the participating teachers were for setting dates for Skype meetings.

To introduce the notion of Urban Tomography to GTU and ETSA-UPV students two Skype lectures were organised. The presentation was sent using WeTransfer and was displayed at the other institutes while the lecture was delivered over Skype.

During “Threshold Matters” a Social Virtual Event was attempted in order to bring the different students together. So far this was not accomplished due to a lack of a proper ICT tool for this (not to our knowledge). As a compromise a Skype discussion / review was organised between the students of GTU and KUL and a tutor from La Salle, as described

above.

For fast and easy communication and notification a closed Facebook group was set up. Students and teachers used this group FB to communicate, post questions, post links and incentives. The closed group has 76 members from three faculties.

To ensure a good understanding of the outputs and enhance their communicative aspects, templates were produced by the students.

Within the different courses in which the “Threshold Matters” learning space was embedded a number of input lectures were organised. The slides of these lectures were made available for the students and teacher using the resources section on the workspace. A next step would be to record the lectures and make them available as video lectures.

The coordinator of the learning space continued to act as moderator during the development of the learning activities. In this role he/she did a follow up of the tasks, contacted partners regarding deadlines, involvement etc. and talked to the students and guided colleagues in using the platform and OIKONET method and tools.

An online survey has been sent to all participants of the Learning Space (LS) “Threshold Matters” at the end of all activities. 8 students (out of 15) from KU Leuven - Sint-Lucas (Ghent) and 10 (out of 13) from Universidad Politécnica de Valencia (UPV) answered the survey giving a total of 18 answers. A full text report on this is the subject of a separate part if the intermediate report. What follows is a summary:

In general, the feedback provided was very positive and included interesting suggestions and reflections.

Students agreed on the fact that the collaborative learning experience was well integrated in the general program of their school. They thought that many tasks were useful also for other courses they had. They particularly valued the exchange of knowledge with students from other institutions. The learning experience allowed them to open their minds.

They had fun in reading and writing comments even though they considered collaboration by commenting too limited. To improve collaborative learning students suggested various improvement activities including having more small-scale communications with the other students in order to improve the feeling of real international collaboration.

When asked about how useful the OIKONET Workspaces was, students responded that the collaborative learning was a bit forced and unnatural. With regards to commenting, students actually preferred the feedback of their own teacher and classmates and considered the ones on the platform less useful because they were mainly very positive and lacked in critical suggestions.

However, most students noted that they would be happy to repeat such a collaborative learning experience. They expressed certainty that with each experience, it can be further improved and that the future of learning goes in this direction as it is a way of getting a broader and more varied perspective on the treated topic.

ESTA-UPV students noted that the collaboration has been interesting because of the possibility to comment and interact with other students.

The presentations from KUL students were based on custom made templates. This was considered very useful because it allowed for an easier lecture of the contents. The tasks were very concrete and this facilitated the understanding. KUL kept strictly to the planning and this has allowed the interactions and reactions to occur in an efficient and effective way.

For the learning of ESTA-UPV students it has been very important to experience the different ways of working and the presentations of the final works. The whole “Threshold Matters” context allowed for a broad and deep reflection on the concept of threshold.

5.8 Conclusions and further steps

During the WP4 meeting in Istanbul DIT expressed an interest and ambition to continue with the “Threshold Matters” learning space. New tasks have thus been created through which the results of the TM will serve as input and inspirations to the DIT students. This is on-going as this report is being written.

DIT have linked a design studio course to the TM learning space as described above.

“Threshold Matters” was a successful pedagogic experience that generated some unique results that could lead to developments in other courses, mainly regarding Urban Tomography. The fact that DIT is currently performing the alternate take is also a good indicator for how this learning experience has inspired new pedagogical practices.

As outlined above the use of the reporter proved to be an important element in opening up the learning space. Through this, links to partners, collaborators etc. were easily established. There is the possibility to extend and investigate how this reporter could be a key figure in constructing a link to the broader academic field and to the general public.

When we organise international workshops it is advisable to introduce these with a social event through which the participants get to know each other. It could be beneficial to the blended learning aspect of the OIKONET project if such an event could be organised at the start of a new learning space. It remains to investigate what (ICT) tools could be used for this.

In this context a cross country task or task(s) could be integrated at the beginning of the learning activities to introduce the collaboration.

Including the WP2 and WP3 subnetworks is definitely another point that needs attention. In that context and in general it should be noted that it is difficult for partners to join a running learning space in the midstream. It is more beneficial for all to be involved from the start (i.e. learning design phase).

The most serious risk to the methodology being carried out in OIKONET is that the learning design can lead to a tight framework with not a lot of room for manoeuvring for modifying tasks, adjusting the sequence, skipping things, adding tasks etc. However, the experience gained will help establish future methodologies.

Predominantly the learning design, as it was developed and structured before the start of the TM learning space (see Appendix C), was followed strictly. This enabled a good follow up and allowed for a maximum of planned collaboration and interaction. Some extra activities and ‘meetings’ were organised (Skype lecture, Skype review, office visit etc...) to support the learning activities in the workshop.

In conclusion it should be noted that despite certain difficulties the interaction and the results so far of the “Threshold Matters” learning space demonstrate that this project is above all a great opportunity to create an innovative learning atmosphere across an academic network that is beneficial for the students and the lecturers alike.

6 HOUSING SYSTEMS

6.1 Introduction

The learning space Housing Systems was implemented for the first time in the fall semester of the academic year 2014/15. The initiative came from the School of Architecture La Salle as part of the elective seminar on “Research on contemporary housing”. Other partners were invited to join the learning space. University of Cyprus collaborated with a postgraduate student and a teacher from the School of Architecture of Valencia collaborated as reviewer of a task.

At the moment of writing this report, a second edition of the learning space is taking place. The partners that are participating are UTH and DIT.

6.2 Topic

The purpose of the seminar is to introduce the concept of housing system. Understanding housing as a system means to take into consideration –all at once–: 1. the components that make a particular system (not only the physical elements such as structural components, but also the dwellers that inhabit the spaces) and 2. the interactions between the components (between structural components and building envelope, between dwellers and spaces). This notion of housing as a system can be traced back to the work of Habraken and the SAR group in the 1960-70s. Nowadays, the notion of system pervades in the Open Building movement.

Understanding housing as a system implies dealing with issues such as industrialization and fabrication (mass customization), dwellers’ participation, and adaptability. The application of ICT to the housing generation enables to address generative modelling (rule-based systems, parametric design).

6.3 Implemented learning activities

The activities that were carried out during the fall semester of 2014/15, those described in the plan described in Appendix D, have been the following:

- **LA74 UNDERSTANDING HOUSING TYPES.** The objective of this Learning Activity is to explore the concept of Housing Type and its relevancy on contemporary domestic architecture.

- **TK1 Create a Housing Collection.** Identifying housing projects in the OIKODOMOS Case Repository according to some specific criteria (the built-in taxonomy of the case repository). Some relevant issues of contemporary architecture - such as Diversity, Sustainability, Diversity, Prefabrication and Mixed-use- have been identified, described and illustrated by the students.

CONTEMPORARY HOUSING
Contemporary housing has many different features. Some of them are: to employ sustainable design techniques, recycled materials, and prefabricated materials; to be flexible by allowing each inhabitant to intervene on the project; and also to integrate different typologies - mixed housing - that provide heterogeneity to the project.

<p>56 houses in Vijfhuizen Architects: Dominic Papp, Jonathan Woodroffe Office: 15353 Location: Vijfhuizen, Netherlands</p>	<p>The density of the housing with the smallness of the plots, and the intense mixture of different cost categories are the main characteristic points of the project. This central idea of a modular housing scheme is not simply ingenious in meeting the demand for individual solutions in a market where economical viability reigns, but actually created a sense of place. Besides that, the buildings are wrapped in a combination of grooved Cumaru planks and aluminum painted, profiled steel sheets, and has solar energy system.</p>	<p>MIXED HOUSING + SUSTAINABILITY + PREFABRICATION</p>	<p>TYPES OF INHABITANT DIFFERENT COST CATEGORIES</p> <p>mixed housing</p>
<p>Artemsgasse 5 Architects: Eva Prochaska, Diemar Eberle, Carlo Baumischlager Location: Österreich, Vienna Dwellings: 108 Completion year: 2008</p>	<p>The structures have different types of inhabitants, urban professionals and senior citizens, which can communicate and interact in the connecting wing. An interesting aspect is the flexibility of the dwellings: for senior citizens, the floor plan gives the opportunity to let nursing staff move in and urban professionals can decide to either separate an office/working area, maybe even a room for children or use the whole apartment. Besides that, the project has solar energy system, and aluminum and wood materials.</p>	<p>MIXED HOUSING + FLEXIBILITY + SUSTAINABILITY</p>	<p>PERSONAL CHOICES VARIABILITY CUSTOMIZATION</p> <p>flexibility</p>
<p>Sebastianstrasse Residential Project Architects: Carlo Baumischlager, Diemar Eberle Location: Dornbirn, Austria</p>	<p>Flexibility appears on the theme of this project: individual living. That includes allowing everyone to choose how many windows they want to have, where they want them to be and how much distance they require from their environment. A white, glass building configuration that presents a different facade according to the user's mood in each individual apartment.</p>	<p>FLEXIBILITY + PREFABRICATION</p>	<p>LOW COST RECYCLED MATERIALS ENERGY SYSTEM</p> <p>sustainability</p>
<p>Residencial House Architects: Felipe Picho-Aguilar, Teresa Barile City: Barcelona, Spain Dwellings: 20 Completion year: 2003</p>	<p>This house is a good example of sustainable building, it has recycled materials, natural ventilation system, water saving system and solar energy system. There are also prefabricated elements related to the facades, like the concrete panels.</p>	<p>SUSTAINABILITY + PREFABRICATION</p>	<p>ALUMINIUM STEEL CONCRETE PANELS MODULATION</p> <p>prefabrication</p>
<p>Kompaktblock Neu-Ulm Architects: Florian Kötter Location: Neu-Ulm, Germany Completion year: 2008</p>	<p>The external structure is divided by staggered balconies, and this arrangement corresponds to different types of habitation inside the building: broad apartments or flats. Furthermore, the sculptured facade promotes the identification of residents with the building: the walls are distinctive by their rhythm and individual apartment is easier to read than in "stacked" housing. Also, the building is built in an ecological design with highly insulating monolithic plastered masonry.</p>	<p>MIXED HOUSING + SUSTAINABILITY</p>	

OIKONET WORKSPACE "HOUSING SYSTEMS"
Learning Activity: Understanding Housing Types. Task 1: Create a Housing Collection
Nathalie Ventura, School of Architecture La Salle

Figure 30. Submission of Task 1 by the student Nathalie Ventura, School of Architecture La Salle

This task was done by La Salle and University of Cyprus students. Students could comment the outcomes of this task. For instance, some of the comments discussed if contemporary housing should fulfil the criteria identified in these examples.

Example of comment by Andronicos Kalli from University of Cyprus:

I believe your poster is discussing some of the most important issues of contemporary housing: adaptability to life and climate changes, adaptability to its users and a redefinition of the boundaries between the public and private realm..

According to example 2, housing architecture is not a static process or a finished deliverable product! It is an adaptable system which takes in consideration social issues and its users need. So how do we design systems that have the flexibility to include decisions made by the users? Can the architect design and predict future needs?

About example 4, I would continue your analysis to recognize how the architect uses vegetation and typology to control privacy between the apartments in a complex and the surrounding of an urban context. Have a look at it in the plan and section, very closely and it can provide you with very strong design tools for your proposal later on...

- TK1 Create a Housing Case Study. The activity consisted in searching in the Case Repository for a case study representative of some of the contemporary domestic architecture themes identified on the previous task. The case studies were documented on both, the OIKODOMOS Case Repository and Workspaces.

Figure 31. Submission of Task 2 by student Davide Serrazanetti, School of Architecture La Salle

Students could comment the outcomes of this task. For example, what they find meaningful in the proposed example: is it a good example of contemporary housing? Why?

- **TK3 Reflecting on the topic of Housing Types.** The activity consisted in writing a short essay summarizing the concept of type in architecture based on the knowledge acquired in previous tasks and in the readings of a selection of texts. The students summarized and compared some aspects related to the discussion about type described by the following authors: Rafael Monéo, Jeremy Till, Leandro Madrazo and Adrian Forty.

The outcomes of this task were commented by teachers from other schools. They formulated questions to students, to make them continue thinking about the issues they have identified.

Example of comment of Carla Sentieri from ETS Arquitectura de Valencia: Hi Davide,

I recommend you to read the book: "las variaciones de la identidad" de Carles Martí, you can find a reflection about the concept of type.

<http://fundacion.arquia.es/es/fundacion/Noticias/Detalle/201>

I think the discussion is: when does Monéo start the process of the project? I think he uses the type as a tool for solving formal relations: "the idea of the type as a cognitive process whereby reality of architecture reveals its essential content, and as the same time as an operating method on the act of projecting." (Carles Martí)

As you say, the idea of "type" must be use as a tool for improving our projects, not

something where start or arrive. If someone arrives to a new conceptual map of relations, never seen before, then it is necessary to look for another "solution" and perhaps this solution will be a type, but the most important thing is the COGNITIVE PROCESS.

- LA80 INTRODUCING HOUSING SYSTEMS. The objective of this L.A. is to introduce the basic concepts of housing systems, based on theoretical precedents (e.g. Habraken's theories, Open Building) .The initially planned Task 4, Task 5 and Task 6 were joined together in only one Task named Task 4_Identifying Housing Systems. To facilitate the activity, some references were provided by the teachers both, readings and projects that illustrated the concept of Housing System.

- Task 4 Identifying Housing Systems. The students analyse and describe selected housing projects in systemic terms by answering the following questions:

1. Which are the elements (components, subsystems) that make the system?
2. Which are the relationships between the elements?
3. Which are the goals of the system?
4. Which is the environment of the system (what is outside the system but interacts with it)?
5. Which are the system internal processes and events (the ways in which the system expresses its activity)?

project
Amsterdam orphanage [Aldo van Eyck]
1955-1960

system
modular system

The elements
2 systems:
grid path

The modules consist of four round columns at the corners with a domed roof of pre-cast concrete on top. The floor is also concrete. The many facades in the building are either a glass wall or a solid wall made with dark brown bricks.

The plan resulted from a horizontal composition of identical modules. This impression is indeed produced by the roof which displays a grid of identical squares. The modules extend according to need and often end up as autonomous entities with a city-like complexity.

The relationship between the elements

individual space individual space individual space individual space

sharing

communal space

interconnected by an internal street

Aldo van Eyck created a decentralized urban node with many points of interaction within the plan. He was interested in a nonhierarchical development of cities and in the Amsterdam Orphanage he created a building with many in-between conditions to break down the hierarchy of spaces.

Internal processes and events

grid + diagonal

The small domes form a grid that extends evenly across the entire building so that the overall pattern can be read at every point. Along the axial lines of this grid, pillars, architraves and solid walls mark off a number of well-anchored, enclosed spaces: the living rooms and adjoining patios, the festive hall, gymnasium and central court.

The units project off two diagonal paths so that each unit has multiple exterior facades. By projecting off of a diagonal within the grid, van Eyck creates an equal amount of negative spaces from the positives he's formed. Each individual unit is then neighbored by its own outdoor space.

The outside system

A larger courtyard is offset diagonally from the residential spaces, and the entrance and administrative spaces connect with the street, the large courtyard, as well as the residential units. Van Eyck avoids creating a central point within the Orphanage by allowing for such fluid connections between all spaces.

The goal of the system The project aims to be a model of growth for the city.

- ORGANIC GROWTH. This decentralized growth model was thought by Aldo van Eyck as a growth model for the city. The internal street aims to be an urban scale element inside the building.
- INDEPENDENCE. Focuses on giving an individual identity to orphan children.
- COMMUNITY. The corridors represents a community feeling. Van Eyck avoids creating a central point within the Orphanage by allowing for such fluid connections between all spaces.

OIKONET WORKSPACE "HOUSING SYSTEMS"
Learning Activity: Introducing Housing System. Task 4. Identifying Housing Systems
Nathalie Ventura, School of Architecture La Salle

Figure 32. Submission of Task 4 by the student Nathalie Ventura, School of Architecture La Salle

- LA81 DEVISING HOUSING SYSTEMS. The objective of this L.A. was to generate housing designs within a housing system. The initially planned TK7 and TK8 were joined together in only one Task named TK5 Devising Housing Systems.

- **TK5 Devising Housing Systems.** The students propose housing designs within a housing system, answering on each proposal the same questions that were addressed on the previous TK4 Identifying Housing Systems.

Figure 33. Submission of Task 5 by the student Davide Serrazanetti, School of Architecture La Salle

6.4 Blended-learning environment

The activities have been carried out in the classroom as well as in the on-line learning environments.

6.4.1 On-site activities

The elective seminar met once a week, during three hours, from October 2013 to February 2014. This time was dedicated to introduce the theoretical basis of the topics, to make presentations of student works, to discuss the comments received through the OIKODOMOS Workspaces environments, and to do the tasks.

6.4.2 On-line activities

OIKODOMOS Workspaces was used to structure the learning activities and to organize the collaborations among the different partners. Both, the comments and the shared Tasks, were submitted on the OIKODOMOS Workspaces.

OIKODOMOS Case Repository was used on different Tasks to create collections that illustrate different Topics. The results of those searching were also submitted on the OIKODOMOS Workspaces to be shared and commented by teachers and students from other institutions.

Some comments among students, were directly written on the OIKODOMOS Case Repository.

6.5 Collaborative activities

From the School of Architecture La Salle, 5 undergraduate students and 2 tutors, participated in the activities. They carried out the tasks described in Section 6.3.

Andronicos Kalli, a postgraduate student from the University of Cyprus, participated in the activities, and made two of the planned tasks.

- **TK1 Create a Housing Collection.** Commenting on several submissions, Andronicos opened different discussions with La Salle's students regarding the criteria to describe contemporary housing.
- **TK1 Create a Housing Collection.** Submitted the Task, finding his own examples. La Salle students commented his selections and compared them with their own findings.

Besides, he was actively involved in commenting and discussing the work done by the students from La Salle, in Barcelona.

Carla Sentieri, professor at the School of Architecture in Valencia, collaborated commenting the work of the students in one of the tasks on the OIKODOMOS Workspaces.

- **Task 3_ Reflecting on the topic of Housing Types:** Carla commented several students submissions on this Task, bringing new references and opening further discussions about different issues such as: Type as the starting point of a design process, the transformation and adaptation of building types or on the relevancy of the concept of Type on nowadays domestic architecture.

The students from La Salle answered back her comments, causing a fruitful exchange about the significance of the concept of type in architecture.

6.6 Outcomes

Some learning resources prepared for the first edition of this learning space can be useful for future editions. They are available in the RESOURCES area of the [OIKODOMOS Workspaces](#).

Bibliography related to Housing Systems:

- Extract of 'General Systems Theory' by Ludwig Von Bertalanffy
- Extract of 'Systems Theory' by Alexander Laszlo
- Extract of 'System of System's by Rusell Ackoff

Bibliography related to Architectural Types:

- Extract of 'Words and Buildings' by Adrian Forty
- Extract of 'Durand and the Science of Architecture' by Leandro Madrazo
- Extract of 'The Background Type' by Jeremy Till

6.7 Evaluation of results

The systematic approach on architectural design conveyed through the topic "housing system" was received with wide interest by the students. Also, due to the novelty of the approach, the students found serious difficulties to develop a deep understanding of the concept and therefore, on devising architectural proposals based on a notion of system. These difficulties forced a change on the original learning plan, increasing the time dedicated to

some tasks and grouping other ones.

In spite of the changes in the original plan, students stated that “*the sequence of tasks was really clear and well done*”. All tasks were related to each other and in a progressive order. For one student, tasks were the most valuable part of the whole learning process (see Learning Space “Housing Systems” – Student’ feedback)

With regard to the level of collaboration between students and teachers of different institutions, some meaningful collaboration occurred in Task 1 Create a Housing Collection and in Task 3 Reflecting on the topic of housing types. In Task 1, students commented the works submitted by other students. In particular, it is worth to mention that the Master student from UCY was commenting the works of his undergraduate peers at La Salle. In Task 3, the works submitted by students were commented by a teacher from another institution (Carla Sentieri, from ETSA-UPV). The format of this submission (a short essay) facilitated this interaction between students and teachers from different universities.

Nevertheless, it would have been desirable to have more institutions involved in the learning space, taking into account that interaction with students and teachers in an international context is very much appreciated by students. Indeed, in the evaluation questionnaires students suggested putting more weight on collaboration, using social media in addition to the OIKODOMOS Workspaces platform, to facilitate a more direct and informal dialogue with other students and teachers.

6.8 Conclusions and further steps

The lessons that can be learned from the first implementation of the learning space are:

- The learning design specifications were useful to get a preliminary understanding of the content and intentions of the learning activities. The sequence of the tasks needs to be coordinated in a specific and a more elaborated document
- There are some tasks dealing with broad issues related to housing that could be reproduced in different and diverse learning spaces. (i.e. Task 1, Task 2, Task 3)
- There are some specific tasks, related to the creations of housing systems that could only be used in courses dedicated to this topic (i.e. Task 4, Task 5 & Task 6)
- The visualization and communication of the on-going activities in real time helps to create unexpected interactions
- The use of social media, in addition to OIKODOMOS Workspaces, could facilitate the interaction of students and teachers in a more direct and informal way.
- The flexibility of a task-based pedagogic structure was proved to be positive on the implementation of the pedagogic plans
- Regular intermediate reports about the results achieved until a certain point in the learning process, would help the institutions involved in a learning space –as well as other institutions following the learning process from outside– to understand the progress that is being made and the objectives that are being pursued.

7 CONTEMPORARY LIVING PATTERNS

7.1 Introduction

This Learning Workspace was created in order to prepare the students participating in the first OIKONET workshop organised in Lisbon, in July 2014. In line with the OIKONET project goals, the Workspace aimed to provide students specialising in architecture and urban planning competencies for working in an international environment. The workspace was thus meant to introduce the topics to be developed during the workshop, and start communication between participants, in order to improve the chances for a successful intensive collaboration week, during the workshop.

Moreover, the preparatory activities were the occasion to involve all fifteen institutions invited to the workshop, who were all members of the “Pedagogy” subnetwork (i.e. WP4). In this way, the Learning Workspace was aiming to foster mutual knowledge and exchanges between all these institutions specialised in architecture and planning education, in the first year of the project.

The “blended learning” methodology could be applied by designing a coherent series of on-line learning activities preceding the workshop, for which the same participants gathered in Lisbon for one week. This method, already developed in the preceding OIKODOMOS project, could thus be used for the first time within the OIKONET project at a larger scale, involving fifteen institutions (about 50 students and 20 tutors).

Besides mutual knowledge, fostering collaboration and applying the “blended learning” model, another main objective, in relation to the main aims of OIKONET, was to explore and combine different disciplinary perspectives on the same topics related to housing.

7.2 Topic

The learning topic was defined in close relation to the subject of the Lisbon workshop entitled “Contemporary living patterns in mass housing in Europe”. It was also directly linked to the urban sites proposed for study during the workshop and with the methodology that the workshop organisers put forward. From this thematic point of view, the Learning activities were heterogeneous, since all the topics of the workshop had to be included:

- housing patterns, architectural forms and urban structures characteristic of two Lisbon areas: Portela de Sacavém (characteristic of mass housing high-rise typology of “towers and slabs” from the 1960s) and Bairro da Liberdade (an informal, unplanned housing area);
- socio-demographic characteristics of the two areas, of Lisbon and of Portugal;
- parametric design tools;
- architecture sustainability and performance;
- participatory processes in housing design and involvement of inhabitants in the design and construction of their own dwellings.

Based on the exploration of the two Lisbon areas and on comparisons with similar case studies in Europe, students had to start reflecting on how contemporary design solutions could be informed by two contrasting housing patterns (i.e. mass housing and informal housing). In addition, the Learning Workspace aimed to introduce students to some of the contemporary paradigms their design solutions had to build on during the workshop (i.e.

parametric design tools, calculations of architecture sustainability and performance and the experience of involving inhabitants in housing design).

7.3 Implemented learning activities

The activities carried out have been the following:

- LA61 URBAN AND ARCHITECTURAL ANALYSIS OF THE PROJECT SITES.

This learning activity allows students and teachers to get familiar with the sites chosen for the workshop in Lisbon.

- **TK1: Historical context analysis: Portela de Sacavém, Lisbon.** Students had to produce a short report in which they had to compare the Portela de Sacavém example to other similar housing programs that students could identify in the cities where they live: densely populated housing designed for the middle class, built by private promoters in the same period as Portela de Sacavém. Those housing programs could include public or private facilities and students were also asked to understand the articulation between the plan and its surroundings. The report could be presented through a series of photographs or a short film.

Portela de Sacavém in Lisbon, Portugal compared to Gellerupparken in Aarhus, Denmark

By Frederik Peter Kæmsgaard, Inger Kirstin Rahbek & Troels Broch | AAU

Figure 34. Fragment from submission for Task 1 by students from AAU

- **TK2 Urban context analysis: Portela de Sacavém and Bairro da Liberdade, Lisbon.** Using a series of maps of Lisbon and of the two sites from several periods, as well as online maps and street view, the students had to reflect on the development of the two districts in time, in relation to the overall structure of the city of Lisbon. They had to analyze the present morphology of the two sites (urban and architectural form), and to identify some characteristics of urban living in the two neighborhoods. They had to produce a report consisting of a series of sketches, synthetic maps and photographs and they had to try to formulate hypothesis and find explanations for the emergence of the present urban configurations and the particularities of the two sites.

Figure 35. Fragment from the submission for Task 2 by students from FASTU

- **TK13 Figure Ground Mapping.** For this task students had to study the existing materials of TK1 and TK2 in this Learning Activity. They had to look at the material to perform three tasks:

1. Formulate a constructive comment on the works done. This is done through using the 'comment' tool in the workspace.
2. From this, identify elements in the uploaded analyses that are gaps of missing pieces of information they think might be useful for understanding the build context in general and the workshop in specific.
3. Produce 3 figure ground maps studying these items. The 3 maps investigate the two workshop sites and compare this with the historical center of Lisbon.

Output: one document using the OIKONET Template.

We did an analysis of the urban character and the infrastructure of the two areas: Bairro de Liberdade and Portela de Sacavém. We made a comparison with an other neighborhood in Lisbon, Castelo de São Jorge. This area is well known for the castle and it's interesting to see how this castle affects his surroundings.

Figure 36. Fragment from the submission for Task 12 by students from KU LEUVEN

- **LA62 THEMATIC REFLECTIONS: PARAMETRIC DESIGN.** The intention of this activity was to introduce students some basic principles of parametric modelling which were to be then applied in the workshop. The task consisted in creating variations of a facade design.

- **TK3 Form principle analysis and schema creation,** (coordinator: Nicolai Steinø, AAU). Based on the lecture, reading and assignment, students had to define form principles for site designs, building envelopes or façade schemes, based on analyses and design work. Based on an examination of the submitted works of others, one other

design had to be combined with the student's own design.

Figure 37. Fragment from the submission for Task 3 by students from BUT

- **LA63 THEMATIC REFLECTIONS: HOME AND SOCIAL CHANGE.** This learning activity focused on social characteristics and specificities of living in mass housing areas in Lisbon, and particularly in the two districts chosen for the Lisbon workshop.

- **TK4 Socio-demographical analysis of the two project sites in Lisbon** (coordinator: Paulette Duarte, UPMF-IUG). The objective of this activity was to explore the social, demographic and economic changes in the Portuguese society. In order to understand the characteristics of the inhabitants of the two Lisbon districts proposed for the workshop, Portela de Sacavém and Bairro da Liberdade, students had to realize a demographic profile of the population using statistical data.

Figure 38. Fragment from the submission for Task 4 by students from IUG_UPMF

- **TK7-8 Summary of the lecture** (coordinator: Sandra Marques Pereira, ISCTE-IUL). Students had to write a summary of the lecture “Home and Social Change”.
- **LA 64 THEMATIC REFLECTIONS: SUSTAINABLE HOUSING.** This learning activity introduced students to principles and concepts of sustainability in architecture and in housing design.
- **TK9 Lecture “Sustainable housing design and performance”**
- **TK10 Reading report.** Students were asked to read chapters "Introduction" and "Conclusion" of reference Mulder, K., Didac, F., van Lente, H. (2011). What is Sustainable Technology? Perceptions, Paradoxes and Possibilities, Greenleaf Publishing Limited? Students had to write a short paper (max. 1000 words) relating the discussion of these chapters to architectural design.
- **LA65 THEMATIC REFLECTIONS: PARTICIPATORY PROCESSES IN HOUSING DESIGN.** This learning activity proposed a reflection on the Portuguese experience of participatory design from the 1970s up to the present.
- **TK11 Documentary “OPERATIONS SAAL”,** João Dias, 2007
- **TK12 Report based on the video and a similar case study.** Students have to write a short manuscript (max. 1000 words) based on the video and a similar case study.

Figure 39. Fragment from the submission for Task 12 by students from FASTU

In terms of outputs from students and especially in terms of collaboration between institutions, the results were lower than expected. A quantitative synthesis of the outcomes can be found in the following table.

Table 1. Outputs produced in the learning space

Learnin g activity	Task number	Number of groups that have completed the task fully	Number of groups that have completed the task partially	Total	Collaborative activities
LA 1	Task 1	3	4	7	Comments from teachers (an average of 1,69 per valid entry)
	Task 2	1	6	7	Collaborative task – based on the analysis formerly produced by the other groups (accomplished by one group)
	Task 13	0	1	1	Collaborative task – based on the analysis formerly produced by the other groups
LA 2	Task 3	0	3	3	The proposed collaborative activity has not been realised by any group
LA 3	Task 4	3	0	3	No collaborative activity proposed
	Tasks 7-8	3	1	4	The proposed collaborative activity has not been realised by any group
LA 4	Tasks 9- 10	4	0	4	No collaborative activity proposed
LA 5	Tasks 11- 12	0	2	2	No collaborative activity proposed

7.4 Blended-learning environment

7.4.1 On-line activities

OIKODOMOS Workspaces was used as a platform where all Tasks descriptions, learning resources, outputs from students and comments were uploaded.

7.4.2 On-site activities

In each institution the meetings between tutors and the students selected for the workshop have been organised in different ways, most often besides regular classes.

The main on-site activity of this Learning space was the final presentation all groups of students made on the first day of the workshop in Lisbon. As a preliminary phase to the Lisbon workshop, the on-line Learning Workspace was meant to initiate discussions that were to be continued during the workshop. On this first day of the workshop, the work done in the preparation phase was presented by each group of students, the sum of their work in different tasks was presented in a poster exhibition and discussed with all workshop participants.

This exercise of synthesising the outputs and presenting them as a starting point for the workshop brought students out of the context of the isolated tasks defined by teachers and encouraged them to interpret in their own way the initial assignments. On this occasion, teachers and students discussed the work done by all groups and these presentations were an essential kick-off phase for the collaboration during the week spent in Lisbon.

7.5 Collaborative activities

Several forms of collaboration between institutions were foreseen:

- Collaboration between tutors from different institutions;
- Collaboration between students from different institutions;
- Collaboration between students and teachers from different institutions.

7.5.1 Collaboration between tutors from different institutions

Each task of the Learning Workspace was conceived and prepared by one or two persons from the same institution. The only form of collaboration between tutors from different institutions, consisted in the exchange of information and materials (resources) necessary for realising the tasks. For example, for the two tasks coordinated by UPMF (France), ISCTE-IUL (Portugal) provided the necessary documentation for analysing the areas under study (i.e. plans, maps and photographs of the two areas and of Lisbon).

7.5.2 Collaboration between students from different institutions

Student work was realised either individually or in a small group of students from the same institution. In addition, several forms of collaboration between students from different institutions have been proposed:

- looking at and commenting other students' work on the OIKODOMOS Workspaces platform;
- using the work of another group as a starting point for one's own work.

In reality, only the first form of collaboration was effective during the Workspace activities. Students looked at the other student's works, but very few comments have been registered on the platform.

In what the second form of collaboration is concerned, it was realised only in one case, when it was imposed by a tutor to the students from his own institution (KU Leuven). This tutor created a supplementary collaborative task for this purpose.

As a preliminary phase to the Lisbon workshop, the on-line Learning Workspace was meant to initiate discussions that were to be continued from the first day of the workshop on. On this first day of the workshop, the work done in the preparation phase was presented by each group of students. This exercise of synthesising the outputs and presenting them as a starting point for the workshop brought students out of the context of the isolated tasks defined by teachers and encouraged them to interpret in their own way the initial assignments. On this occasion, teachers and students discussed the work done by all groups and these presentations were an essential kick-off phase for the collaboration during the week spent in Lisbon.

7.5.3 Collaboration between students and tutors from different institutions

Finally, a third form of collaboration was proposed for the Learning Workspace, which consisted of feed-back given by teachers who commented students' work on the OIKODOMOS Workspaces platform. First and foremost, the initiators of each task were in charge of discussing students' outputs, but comments and questions from all other tutors were highly encouraged.

7.6 Outcomes

Some learning resources, especially videos, can be useful for other learning activities. They are available on the OIKONET Channel or directly on OIKODOMOS Workspaces, as Resources.

These learning resources are:

- Video documentary: Portela de Sacavém, Ana Vaz Milheiro, Dinamia'CET, ISCTE-IUL;
- Video lecture "Form principle analysis and schema creation", Nicolai Steinø, AAU;
- Video lecture "Home and Social Change", Sandra Marques Pereira, Dinamia'CET, ISCTE-IUL;
- Video lecture "Sustainable housing design and performance", Vasco Moreira Rato, ISCTE-IUL;
- Reading material: Mulder, K., Didac, F., van Lente, H. (2011). What is Sustainable Technology? Perceptions, Paradoxes and Possibilities, Greenleaf Publishing Limited;
- Video documentary: "OPERATIONS SAAL", João Dias, 2007.

The analysis and digital presentations from students of different case studies of mass housing in their own countries are a valuable collection that can be used for further learning activities on this topic, enabling a comparative perspective.

7.7 Evaluation of results

The majority of participants, and especially teachers, considered the preparatory learning activities as being extremely important for facilitating the work during the workshop, especially because the workshop itself lasted only five and a half days, which was quite short. Besides preparing students and getting to know each other, the Learning Workspace allowed collecting learning and teaching materials, valuable for the workshop but also besides it.

However, several problems have been identified, especially concerning collaboration between partners. In the collaboration between teachers, a heterogeneous character and a lack of overall coherence resulted from the lack of coordination between the different parts of the Learning Workspace created and coordinated by different partners. Moreover, the preparatory activities of the Learning Workspace and the activities of the workshop were not well correlated. Therefore the importance of the preparatory activities was diminished. A better initial coordination of the Learning Workspace involving a larger number of participating teachers and a better coordination between the Workspace and the workshop would be very beneficial in the future.

Time management and planning was a big difficulty, because preparatory activities had to be done in parallel with regular activities of each institution, at the end of the spring semester, when students are generally involved in exams and other end-year projects. Moreover, the academic calendars and the exact periods of time when students from different universities could actually work on the proposed assignments were largely unknown when the activities were initiated.

Because of lack of time, students' outputs were realised very late, when no more time was left for commenting and exchanging ideas about their work before the workshop. Altogether, no communication between students from different institutions took place during the preparatory learning activities, even if that had been one of the aims of the Learning Workspace. Since the OIKODOMOS Workspaces platform proved rather difficult to use and especially unfit for fostering a more informal dialogue, participants suggested complementing it with additional communication tools (like a Facebook group) in the future. Online meetings before the workshop could also be beneficial, in order to introduce each other.

7.8 Conclusions and further steps

The experience was successful in preparing students to perform in an international environment, by getting acquainted to a foreign context. It was also useful for improving both students' communication skills, including oral, writing, graphic representation, digital presentation etc. Looking at each other's work gave significant results, even if this form of collaboration is difficult to assess. Such a workspace should be organised also in the future in order to prepare the next OIKONET workshops. However, several aspects should be amended.

In terms of content, in the future, more emphasis should be placed on the definition of concepts and terms, in order to gain in accuracy and fully understand disciplinary differences and eventually overcome them. Collaboration with the "Research" subnetwork on these issues would be particularly useful.

The number of tasks for pre-workshop activities should be reduced, in order to make the whole Workspace more easily understandable to all participating students and teachers and thus facilitate their work and their collaboration. Less tasks would also leave more time for commenting, for collaboration and for more informal discussions allowing students to get to know each other before the on-site experience of the workshop.

In order to foster more collaboration and to communicate easier, complementary communication tools should be introduced, as for example, a Facebook Group.

8 CONCLUSIONS

Designing and implementing the learning spaces in collaboration has contributed to forge links among the partners in the network, to exchange knowledge about various matters related to housing studies, as well to share pedagogical methods and experiences. As a result of this collaborative work, it has been possible to come up with new strategies and procedures –which have not been developed in the previous OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus projects– to improve the process of designing the learning and also the implementation of the planned activities. The template which has been developed in the project to describe, collaboratively, a learning plan before starting with the implementation of the learning activities constitutes an example of this (see Appendices). With regard to the implementation of the activities, a consensus has been reached to complement the formal learning structure implemented with the aid of OIKODOMOS Workspaces with social web tools which enable a more informal, personal communication between learners. In this regard, it is worth to mention the use of Twitter and Facebook groups as complementary spaces of the work done in Workspaces, something which was not done in the previous OIKODOMOS project.

Some other conclusions which can be drawn from the experiences reported in the different learning spaces are the following:

With regard to the learning design process

- Agreeing on a template to create the learning plan of a learning space, before this is implemented, has represented a step forward with regard to the processes which have been used before the partners in previous projects.
- Coming up with a common learning structure helps to bring together the multiple approaches to housing adopted at the different schools. On the other hand, the structure should be flexible enough to be adapted to the specific conditions of each participating school
- Identifying the learning outcomes right at the start of the learning design process, continues being uneasy to most teachers in architecture schools. However, they should be a constituent part of the learning design process
- A remaining challenge is to involve researchers in the planning of the learning activities (as well as in the evaluation of the student works). The themes addressed in a learning space (e.g. habitat regeneration strategies) are themselves research themes. Therefore, teachers could benefit from the knowledge that researchers can provide about the latest stand of the research on the topic, including relevant publications which can be used as references. The open approach adopted in the design of the learning spaces favours the interweaving of learning and research, teachers and researchers
- A blended-learning approach helps to overcome the division between on-site and on-line activities by creating new learning spaces. In this regard, the most effective mechanism to create a sense of place and a feeling of community is still through face-to-face meetings. Whenever is possible, it is recommendable to meet face-to-face at the start of the learning process before starting the on-line collaboration. Likewise, at each school, teachers need to come up with their own strategies to bring to the classroom the outcomes of the shared activities performed on-line

With regard to the implementation of the learning activities

- It is necessary that the teachers involved in a collaborative learning process maintain a fluent and constant communication during the whole period of implementation. Agreeing on the communication channels to be used, it is fundamental to keep the conversation alive during the whole process. These channels can be manifold: email, Twitter, Facebook group and also the Bulletin Board in the Workspaces environment. All of these channels, especially those of the social web, need to be regularly fed with information. In this regard, to appoint a person to be in charge of providing information during the whole learning process can be helpful, communicating what is being done in a group in a way that is intelligible to other partners (as it was done, for example, in the latest implementation of “Threshold Matters”).
- It is necessary to keep track of the progress of the learning activities, summarizing at specific points during the learning process what has been achieved so far, in a way that it can be easily understandable to the learners involved in the activities, and also to other interested partners –inside and outside the OIKONET network. This can be achieved by releasing regular reports, describing the stages of the learning process, illustrated with works of the students. Such summaries are useful to get a quick overview of what is being done in a learning space, thus avoiding having to search within the Workspaces environment, or being confused by continuous posting in social web environments.
- Participating teachers need to come up with their own strategy to link the activities performed in the shared learning spaces with those carried out at their courses. The level of integration between both can differ, from full integration (as in the case of an elective course exclusively dedicated to interact with other partners, like in the courses in La Salle or in KU Leuven) to punctual interactions with the tasks carried out in the learning space (e.g. commenting the work done by students in other schools, using the learning resources facilitated by other partners, attending a video lecture on a specific theme delivered by a third partner).
- The work done in a learning space –the learning structure of activities and tasks, the resources collected and the works done by students– is a valuable learning resource which can be exploited later by other partners. On the other hand, a continuous aggregation of new learning activities and tasks can eventually undermine the coherence of the learning structure to the point the overall work might become unintelligible to later users. To avoid this, it is recommended to create subsequent editions of learning spaces, creating each time a new learning structure adapted to the needs of the new users, although using the learning activities and tasks already created which can be accessed in the SystemAdmin environment of Workspaces.
- In the lack of a common understanding of the objectives of a learning space, or the impossibility to agree on a timetable, there is a risk that different schools would work in parallel without interacting with each other. To avoid this, it is crucial to have a plan which includes links between the works done at each school with the shared activities.
- Students and teachers need to be aware of the limitations and requirements that come along while collaborating in an on-line learning environment. Still, the idea that these environments are meant to “upload” an assignment is prevailing. Rather, they should understand that an on-line learning environment is a communication space, with its own rules and requirements. This means that it is necessary to make a proper use of graphical and textual languages within this communication space, to be sure that the ideas that are expressed through them will reach other students at teachers, at other places and institutions.

- The role of a learning space coordinator is fundamental for the success of the shared learning activities. The coordinator is responsible of maintaining the consistency of the common work, to keep all participants informed throughout the whole process, and to highlight the value of what is being achieved.

With regard to evaluation of the activities:

- The evaluation questionnaires need to be jointly produced (adapted on the basis of a template) with the collaboration of the designers of each learning space. In fact, the evaluation questionnaire should be a constituent part of the learning plan.

- The vocabulary of the evaluation questionnaires needs to reflect the actual learning experience. One of the difficulties in this regard is to name what is being done in an open-ended learning space, of undefined limits –conceptual, physical– as the ones generated through the collaboration in the learning space.

APPENDICES

8.1 APPENDIX A. Learning plan: Introduction to Housing

1. Theme

Introduction to housing

2. Description

The purpose of this Workspace is to identify, to analyse and to apply strategies in order to start with the design of a house. They have to learn to recognize the tools of the discipline, recognize basic structural systems, perform conceptual models, analyse projects and recognize patterns of functioning in order to be able to design a house.

3. Course level(s)

1st year students and 2nd year students, but also the rest of students could use the tasks ETSA-UPV (P2): Bachelor students/ 2nd year students design studio, elective. During the 2nd semester 2015: 1st year students design studio. UCY (P15): During the fall semester 2014 UCY will participate in the workspace with 4th year students who will attend a course on residential architecture. During the 2nd semester UCY will participate with 2nd year students who will attend a housing design studio.

AF (P26): During the fall 2014 and spring 2015 semesters Belgrade University will contribute with examining possibilities and collecting materials for a MOOC creation.

KUL (P4): No students, teacher involvement

DIT (P29): No students in 1st semester, teacher involvement

4. Coordinator

Carla Sentieri/ ETSA-UPV, Valencia, Spain (P2)

5. Participating partners

- Nadia Charalambous, Department of Architecture, University of Cyprus (P15)
- Mirjana Devetakovic, Faculty of Architecture of Belgrade University (P26)
- Tomas Ooms, Faculty of Architecture KU Leuven, Belgium (P4)
- Jim Roche, Dublin Institute of Technology (P29)

6. Learning objectives

- *General aim of the learning space*

Through the production of a series of learning activities students aim to understand the difference between a house and a home. Student should be able to make appropriate use of different representation techniques (verbally, textual and graphic-digital and analogue) in order to communicate the ideas (concepts and design proposals) in an effective manner and they should be able to demonstrate team working skills through their contribution to the project.

- *Specific learning outcomes*

- The student should be able to recognize the elements and the dimension of a space
- The student should be able to demonstrate coherence and continuity in the development of the design process
- The student should be able to critique their own work and that of others by reference to established models of good practice and the appropriate standards
- The student should be able to illustrate the importance of spatial imagination and

presentation (e.g. expressed by sketches, models)

- The student should be able to describe the social determinants of housing design (e.g. dispositions, typology, national policy and standards)
- The student should be able to demonstrate knowledge of the relevant theoretical background

7. Partners contribution

ETSA-UPV (P2)

- Specific expertise: with examples of housing I have built in design studio; teaching and research of domestic space studio for the past 10 years
- Teaching and learning resources (e.g. Online or other formats): studio blog with pdf of examples of houses on the workspace.
- Assessment activities: discussions in a group, online comments from partner institutions possible
- Past experiences / courses: introduction to housing

UCY (P15)

- Specific expertise: relevant research work through the Urban Segregation and Conflict Studies lab; teaching of domestic space studio for the past 10 years
- Teaching and learning resources (e.g. Online or other formats) studio blog and postgraduate course blog (includes all learning material)
- Assessment activities and feedback; analysis of precedents and contexts; new proposals; encourage joint assessment and feedback through sharing of our assessment tools.
- Past experiences / courses taught at UCY; Studio on domestic space and postgraduate course on urban (including residential) segregation

AF-Belgrade (P26)

- Specific expertise Various representation techniques in housing, including basic 3D modelling techniques in Sketch Up
- Teaching and learning resources (e.g. Online or other formats: Past virtual environments and students submissions
<http://elearning.rcub.bg.ac.rs/moodle/course/view.php?id=269>
<http://elearning.rcub.bg.ac.rs/moodle/mod/forum/view.php?id=6274>
<http://elearning.rcub.bg.ac.rs/moodle/mod/forum/view.php?id=5912>
- Assessment activities: Organization of 2 joint videoconferences
- Past experiences / courses: 3D Visual Communications, last 5 years, Integrated modelling, CAAD principles

8. Learning Activities

“Introduction to housing” will be implemented in two courses: the ETSA-UPV second year Design Studio and the UCY 4th year course and 2nd year design studio. KUL and DIT will

participate with the collaboration of the teachers. AF_ Belgrade is working outside the workspace, with the future and possible MOOC. The topic of Introduction to housing will thus be tackled in different context and in different ways. Each course has a different track of sequence of tasks. Some tasks will be done collectively, others will be done just by one school and can be used for other activities.

These are the learning activities and the tasks for the first semester. Another template will be created to describe the activities of the second semester.

LA53 RECOGNIZING SPACE

- Description

This learning activity focuses on the analysis of the interior spaces of a house: rooms and space-defining elements, furniture, pieces and other objects inside the rooms, deal with the house as a home and work with the inside space to recognize its dimensions and particularities.

- Keywords

space, size, home

- Learning outcomes

- The student should be able to make appropriate use of different representation techniques (verbally, textual and graphic-digital and analogue) in order to communicate the ideas (concepts and design proposals) in an effective manner.
- The student should be able to demonstrate team working skills through their contribution to the project.
- The student should be able to recognize the elements and the dimension of a space
- The student should be able to establish the graphic criteria for the representation of the project on paper
- The student should be able to critique their own work and that of others by reference to established models of good practice and the appropriate standards
- The student should be able to illustrate the importance of spatial imagination and presentation (e.g. expressed by sketches, models)
- The student should be able to describe the social determinants of housing design (e.g. dispositions, typology, national policy and standards)

The following tasks are included in the learning activity “Recognizing space”: Tasks (TK1, TK2, TK3, TK4, TK8, TK10)

- Task 1 What is a house?

The goal of this task is to distinguish the concepts of house and home. Students are expected to address issues such as: what makes you feel good at a home? These reflections are summarized in a A3 document combining different materials and techniques (texts, drawings, photographs).

- Task 8 Collective housing

Examples of collective housing projects are presented and discussed in the classroom. Afterwards, the students will make their own reflections about collective housing and present them in an A3 document.

LA54 DERIVING IDEAS FROM TEXTS

- Description

This activity could be named: interpretation of an idea.

Argumentation is very important for architects, it is the way we explain our ideas to people who are not familiar with drawings. Also, the interpretation of a text is never unique. The purpose of this activity is to explore the transformation of the ideas described in a text- or, more precisely, the interpretation of those ideas- into drawings that will become inhabited spaces.

- Keywords

Idea, interpretation, home

- Learning outcomes

-The student should be able to integrate and synthesise relevant information into a new context and solution, based on a clear concept

-The student should be able to illustrate the importance of spatial imagination and presentation (e.g. expressed by sketches, models)

-The student should be able to critique their own work and that of others by reference to established models of good practice and the appropriate standards

-The student should be able to develop a professional working basis of processes, organisation and communication skills appropriate to their professional practice (e.g. design and construction)

-The student should be able to demonstrate the ability to search, adapt and apply information to the problem in hand

-The student should be able to makes appropriate use of different representation techniques (verbally, textual and graphic-digital and analogue) in order to communicate the ideas (concepts and design proposals) in an effective manner.

-The student should be able to demonstrate team working skills through personal contribution to a joint presentation

These tasks are not going to be implemented during by the rest of institutions/group (TK5, TK6, TK7)

LA55 PRECEDENT ANALYSIS

- Description

The purpose of this activity is to learn from precedents, to understand the factors that influence residential architecture, to identify solutions provided from previous projects and to transform them into new ones.

- Keywords

house, analysis, courtyard house

- Learning Outcomes

-The student should be able to analyse the multiple variables that influence existing housing designs

-The student should be able to define the issues affecting the actual design of residential architecture (social changes, globalisation, materials, local context...)

- The student should be able to make appropriate use of different representation techniques (verbally, texturally and graphic-digital and analogue) in order to communicate their ideas (concepts and design proposals) in an effective manner.
- The student should be able to recognize the functional, spatial and structural organization of a house.
- The student should be able to demonstrate understanding of boundaries and scales (within the house and between the house and the neighbourhood and urban space) in relation to public-private interfaces.

The following tasks are included in the learning activity “Precedent Analysis”.

- Task 11 Analysis of domestic architecture

Analysis of international examples of domestic architecture (context, users, social, economic, environmental variables).

LA58 USER PROFILE ANALYSIS

Description

Houses are a complex expression of the social and individual worlds of their occupants, in which social structure, the patterns and conventions of everyday life seem to be closely related to the idiosyncratic and many times chaotic circumstances of people’s everyday lives. Students are encouraged to understand that the design of a “home” needs to address the practicalities of everyday living while responding at the same time to the owner’s idiosyncrasy, personality and dreams. It is therefore important to be able to analyse, understand and address possible users’ profile.

Keywords

Users’ profile, analysis, home

Learning outcomes

- The student should be able to analyse potential user profiles that demonstrate understanding of the relationship between social and spatial patterns
- The student should be able to makes appropriate use of different representation techniques (verbally, textual and graphic-digital and analogue) in order to communicate the ideas (concepts and design proposals) in an effective manner.

The following tasks are included in the learning activity “User profile analysis”.

- TK12 Analysis of potential domestic users

Students are randomly given existing user profiles and are asked to describe their daily routines, hobbies, personalities, spatial patterns.

LA59 CONTEXT ANALYSIS

Description

Homes may many times reflect differences between ethnic, cultural and social categories, including gender divisions between men and women or generational differences between adults and children. Many times homes may reflect differences in environmental conditions (climate, light, air, topography). The way these differences are found in the house may vary in different cultures and different geographic areas and may be observed in the way domestic

space is designed and organized. Students are encouraged to understand through this activity the ways in which domestic space is site/context specific.

Keywords

Context analysis, domestic space

Learning outcomes

- The student should be able to apply the principles of urban analysis
- The student should be able to demonstrate the ability to search, adapt and apply information to the problem in hand
- The student should be able to makes appropriate use of different representation techniques (verbally, textual and graphic-digital and analogue) in order to communicate the ideas (concepts and design proposals) in an effective manner.
- The student should be able to develop awareness for various processes shaping residential architecture.
- The student should be able to develop an understanding of the multiple and complex variables in relation to context that influence existing and new proposals
- The student should be able to demonstrate understanding of boundaries and scales (within the house and between the house and the neighbourhood and urban space) in relation to public-private interfaces.

TK13_Visual mapping of context

Students are asked to respond to specific sites - contexts given by their tutors employing visual ethnography methods. They are asked to represent context specific characteristics (cultural, social, and environmental) through both digital and printed photo essays.

LA60 AT HOME. NEW DESIGNING PROPOSALS.

Description

Taking into consideration all the work produced through the preceding tasks students are asked to design a "home" in a specific context that addresses local conditions and culture, the practicalities of everyday living and the users' profile, personality and dreams.

Understanding the context bound relationship between the spatial structure of domestic space and the social life of the inhabitants is one of the central challenges of this studio. We are interested in the ways in which the home as a spatial form, relates to the social, the cultural, the individual in the context of the increasingly divided, complex and differentiated experiences of contemporary life.

Keywords

House, design, domestic space

Learning outcomes

- The student should be able to apply compositional skills on the level of a basic dwelling; expression of strategic development pre-scenarios of the analysed site
- The student should be able to make a complex synthesis of cross-disciplinary approaches to the project.
- The student should be able to integrate and synthesise relevant information into a new context and solution, based on a clear concept
- The student should be able to discuss and present development scenarios for the given site.

-The student should be able to demonstrate the ability to search, adapt and apply information to the problem in hand

-The student should be able to makes appropriate use of different representation techniques (verbally, textual and graphic-digital and analogue) in order to communicate the ideas (concepts and design proposals) in an effective manner.

-The student should be able to create designs (architectural, urban design, planning) that satisfy aesthetic, cultural, social and technical requirements.

Tasks (TK15, TK16)

9. Sequence of tasks

LA 53	TK 1	TK 2	TK 3	TK 4				TK 8			TK 10						
LA 54					TK 5	TK 6	TK 7										
LA 55									TK 9		TK 11						
LA 58												TK 12					
LA 59													TK 13	TK 14			
LA 60															TK 15	TK 16	TK 17

LA53	TK1			
LA55		TK8	TK11	
LA58				TK13
LA59				
LA60				

CYP	01/10 20/10	01/10 20/10	01/11 15/11	01/11 15/11
ETSA	01/10 20/10	01/10 20/10	01/11 15/11	01/11 15/11
KUL	comments	comments	comments	comments
DIT	comments	comments	comments	comments

The tasks we are going to do this semester are: 1,8,11, and 13.

Jim Roche and – DIT (P29) Tomas Ooms – KUL (P4) will participate with comments to the works.

	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	April	May	June
ETSA-UPV		TK1 TK8	TK11 TK13			TK1 TK2 TK3 TK4	TK5 TK6 TK7		TK15 TK16	TK15 TK16
UCY		TK1 TK8	TK11 TK13		TK1	TK11 TK12	TK13	TK 15 TK 16	TK15 TK16	
AF BELGRADE										

ETSA-UPV students will make comments about Tasks of UCY’s group, for example:

- Is there anything new for you in this presentation? What and why?
- Is there anything else that you can consider important? What and why?
- An evaluation of graphic presentation (if you have a rubric, I can use the same)

10. Define ways of collaboration / collaboration levels:

(e.g. Cross-Institutional, Trans-Institutional, Link to other WPs)

	CROSS-INSTITUTIONAL	TRANS-INSTITUTIONAL	LINKS TO OTHER WPS
ETSA-UPV	X	X	
UCY	X	X	X with WP2
AF BELGRADE			

11. In addition to the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus tools (WS, Case Repository) what other collaboration tools / environments are you using? What for?

Tools used by all participants (e.g. Facebook group, Dropbox, Google+)

	Facebook	Dropbox	Google+	Poliformat	Blog
ETSA-UPV		X		X	
UCY		X	X		X
AF BELGRADE					

At UCY everything related to the studio course is uploaded by both tutors and students on a blog: Athome201.net. Dropbox is mostly used to upload reference material and Reading. Google is mainly used for coordination (schedules, presentation dates etc).

12. What are your expectations regarding the impact / influence of using the in the collaborative learning space.

ETSA-UPV (P2)

For you as a teacher?

- To improve my pedagogic methodology
- To reflect about the learning and teaching process
- To improve my English

For your students?

- To know what is happening in other schools
- To improve their knowledge of English
- To have the opportunity to comment on other student's work

For your course?

- To create new tasks and assignments
- To comment the works on line_ use write word for the comments

For your institution?

- To establish new relations between schools
- To open up the possibilities for exchanges of students and teachers

UCY (P15)

For you as a teacher?

- To incorporate blended learning in my teaching

- To get feedback from colleagues in different academic environments
- To get familiar with different and diverse teaching methods and learning resources

For your students?

- They will be exposed to different cultural and academic contexts
- They will be able to experience different methods of learning through the virtual campus
- They will have the opportunity to comment on other students' work but also receive feedback from both peers and tutors

For your course?

- It will be enriched both in terms of teaching methodology but also in terms of references and learning resources
- It will gain from constructive criticism from both students and colleagues abroad

For your institution?

- To enhance the possibilities for international networking and collaboration
- To increase students and staff exchanges

AF_BELGRADE (P26)

For you as a teacher?

- To extend the level of blended learning already applied in previous courses.
- To compare different e-learning platforms.
- To get familiar with different and diverse teaching methods and learning resources.

For your students?

- They will be exposed to different cultural and academic contexts.
- They will enrich their learning experience by being exposed to an international learning context.
- They will have a responsibility to comment other students' results within common or similar learning tasks.

For your course?

- It will be enriched both in terms of references and learning resources.
- It will contribute to the ongoing studio activities (since it is not part of the studio teaching).
- It will gain from constructive criticism from colleagues abroad.

For your institution?

- It will increase its international visibility
- It will open towards the newest trends in teaching architecture.

13) Please check the project goals to which your learning space will contribute:

Promoting cooperation between research, education and society , by bringing together stakeholders from different areas to formulate and discuss contemporary problems regarding housing at a European and global scale.	x
Providing students, teachers, researchers and other stakeholders with the competences necessary to work in a readily accessible international environment	x
Encouraging the active participation of these stakeholders in the creation of innovative learning spaces which overcome disciplinary and institutional boundaries	
Facilitating cooperation between different academic programs which include housing (in its different dimensions) as subject matter.	x
Fostering physical and virtual mobility across partner institutions, by means of workshops, seminars, conferences and shared learning activities in blended learning scenarios dedicated to study contemporary housing issues.	
Contributing to the internationalisation of the European cooperation , incorporating third countries to the network. This will facilitate the exchange and mobility at the international level, preparing the ground for further cooperation among network partners in future programs (Erasmus Mundus).	x
Promoting new forms of international cooperation , through the design and implementation of shared learning activities carried out following a blended learning approach with the digital environments of the OIKODOMOS virtual campus.	x
Establishing evaluation procedures to guarantee the quality of the pedagogic activities to be implemented by network partners, in mixed formal and informal pedagogical settings.	x
Establishing evaluation procedures to guarantee the quality of the pedagogic activities to be implemented by network partners, in mixed formal and informal pedagogical settings.	
Reinforcing the societal roles of academic institutions in a culturally and linguistically diverse Europe, by embedding the learning activities in those social milieus in which solutions for housing problems are needed (integration, immigration) thus activating knowledge through interaction with society.	
Enhancing interdisciplinarity and transdisciplinarity , by creating new learning spaces which bring together different disciplines into the solution of housing problems.	x
Contributing to the development of technology enhanced learning , embedding ICT in the learning processes and learning structures.	x

8.2 APPENDIX B. Learning plan: Habitat Regeneration Strategies

1. Theme

Habitat Regeneration Strategies

2. Description

The OIKONET learning space “Habitat Regeneration Strategies” is aimed at supporting a wide range of learning activities in examining actual European and world experiences in regeneration of cities, with a particular interest in the issues of liveability, housing and resilience.

Considering urban habitat regeneration integrative, urban design provides space for developing the so called "glocal" place, as an urban pattern that integrates global and local environmental issues, standards, cultures, and ways of building. Many towns have wasted, unused or under-used land, brownfields. Urban regeneration strategies give them the opportunity for redeveloping such areas and for creating much better liveable environment. Regeneration represents such multi-sectorial interventions to city brownfields, which can result in the environmental, social and economic improvements of the area. According to Eurocities “urban regeneration is at the core of city planning. Urban regeneration can be defined as the integrated local redevelopment of deprived areas (neighbourhood, city, metropolitan area). It covers many aspects of city life: physical, social, economical and environmental. Approaches depend on a city’s history, and therefore policies must be integrated and area-based.”¹

Urban regeneration involves the renewal of urban areas and settlements. Regeneration strategies are from many points of view specific. They should:

- **Integrate multi-sectorial and all level government investigation and coordination.** They should consider the demographic changes, political, economical and structural issues, environmental and social issues, good design, etc. According Chris Brown „urban regeneration is concerted social, economic and physical action to help people experiencing multiple deprivation reverse decline and create sustainable communities”.
- **Create holistic visions and good designs, which should be in the core of the regeneration process.** According Jon Ladd (former chief exec. BURA, British Urban Regeneration Assoc.) „urban regeneration is a comprehensive and integrated vision and action, which leads to the solution of urban problems and which seeks for the sustainable improvement in the area.” At the same time the comprehensive holistic vision should reflect local conditions. „Each strategy is specific, different, there is no common template“.
- **Engage people, stakeholders in participatory processes,** “not only to make people satisfied by the results of the process of regeneration, but to make them proud to be a part of it, as well...” (John Ireland)². It reflects Castells project identity that is needed for tackling

¹ Urban planing/regeneration, Eurocities, 2013, <http://www.eurocities.eu/eurocities/issues/urban-planning-regeneration-issue> (retrieved March 2015)

² Ten Ways to define regeneration, Building, 16 February 2006, <http://www.building.co.uk/10-ways-to-define-regeneration/3062794.article> (retrieved March 2015)

with processes of globalization in creative clusters of intellectuals, entrepreneurs, decision makers, students, etc. In that manner art and creativity become integrative factors for conflicts of values, interests, different viewpoints. This process leads towards ‘drawing’ a common future image. Integrative urban design uses Habermas’ communicative action to bound instrumental, collaborative, strategic, interdisciplinary, technical and artistic dimension in ‘open play’ of imagining common future place.

- **Engage public sector leadership.** Physical urban regeneration requires public sector financial support.... Regeneration of waterfronts is one of the main issues concerning housing. Therefore, the learning activities will focus on urban habitat regeneration emphasising housing and participatory dimension

3. Course level(s)

AF_Belgrade – 3rd year students , FASTU – 4th year Bachelor, 4th year students Volgograd, UPMF Grenoble – 2nd year students .

4. Coordinator

Tatjana Mrdjenovic, Mirjana Devetakovic, University of Belgrade

5. Participating partners

- Viera Joklova, FASTU Faculty of Architecture Slovak University of Technology Bratislava
- Mirjana Devetakovic, Tatjana Mrdjenovic, University of Belgrade, Faculty of Architecture
- Elina Krasilnikova, VSUACE Volgograd State University of Architecture and Civil Engineering
- Adriana Diaconu, University Pierre Mendès-France of Grenoble
- Gregor Herda, UN Habitat

6. Learning objectives

The course is aimed at developing knowledge and skills among participants (Public, Civil, Private stakeholders on various levels of governance) and partners on:

- Participatory process in urban habitats regeneration considering sustainability principles;
- Role of integrative urban design in the process;
- Methods and techniques that can be used;
- The nature and options of facilitating, moderating, guiding the process; sustainable urban habitat regeneration.

The methodology is based on UN-Habitat approach in local community development which fosters sustainable, integrative principles among stakeholders, developmental sectors, institutions, levels of governance. Specifically, the methodology used in the course is context based (e.g. tailor made) participatory process, specific to local issues. This will be implemented as an iterative and cyclical process of learning that is growing in each phase, widening the level of participation among stakeholders and partners: from reflecting towards collaboration.

- Students of architecture will learn how to participate in creation of regeneration strategies
- Students of geography will examine different urban morphologies within the regeneration processes of riverbanks.
- All students will learn how to identify strategies behind observed regeneration examples, with particular interest in habitat issues
- All students will learn what habitat is and how their disciplines are related to habitat issues.

7. Partners contribution

AF_BELGRADE (P 26)

- Managing Workspace
- Integrative urban design
- Participatory urban design
- Post-disaster regeneration strategies
- Flood adaptation measures

FASTU (P3)

- Participation in the Learning Space
- Sustainable and eco-friendly design, Integrative urban design, Waterfront rehabilitation strategies
- Teaching and learning resources , principles on sustainable rehabilitation (presentation), Bratislava – Petržalka housing and urban fabric development (presentation), tasks description
- Assessment activities – online presentations via videoconferencing, commenting partners' students
- Active cooperation with partners on the LA and Task definition, and creation, communication with municipality, social activists and research partners in order to enhance the learning portfolio and collaborative activities.

FAVSUACE (P31)

- Participation in the Learning Space
- Lecture online, videoconference, articles, monograph, publication of the results in internet-resource (<http://green-city.su/>) and in the magazine (<http://proektnv.ru/>)
- Post-industrial and depressive territories regeneration strategies
- Landscape urbanism, regeneration of post-industrial and waterfront territories

8. Learning Activities

The learning process has been structured it three main learning activities and one general introductory activity.

LA69 – The Workspace Intro

This learning activity is aimed at general familiarizing the participants with the prepared Workspace. It contains two tasks.

- **TK4** requires student individual introduction illustrated with recent designs or other referent work.
- **TK5** offers a possibility for a group introduction in the case that the learning within the workspace is going to be realised only in groups.

LA70 – Urban Habitat Regeneration and Integrative Urban Design in Sustainable Development

This learning activity introduces the main issues of sustainable development, habitat and integrative urban design. It is explorative and is focused on successful examples of habitat regeneration worldwide.

It consists of several tasks TK6, TK7, TK8 (and TK18 added in second semester of the Workspace use).

In TK6 Exploring the Case of Ciutat Vella, Barcelona, groups of students are required to explore the case of habitat regeneration of Ciutat Vella, Barcelona, as one of the most successful habitat regeneration examples in Europe.

- **TK7** is focused on habitat in general and activities of UN Habitat. It is oriented toward the UN Habitat Urban Lectures, available online at: <http://unhabitat.org/urban-knowledge/urban-lectures/>.
- **TK8** Exploring the examples of urban regeneration strategies – In these task students are required to find successful examples of habitat regeneration worldwide and to recognize strategies behind.

LA71 – Creating Habitat Regeneration Strategies

In this learning activity the groups of students from different institutions focus on assigned cases, be it local or international, for which they are going to participate in creation of habitat regeneration strategy.

TK9 Habitat analyses. The task is aimed at analysis of the case of the habitat selected for intervention.

TK10 Urban morphology and regeneration of riverbanks- A task created for geography students, requires a morphological analysis of the riverbanks of the cities of participating institutions: Bratislava, Grenoble, Belgrade and Volgograd.

TK11 Urban mobility. The task is focused on urban mobility in Petržalka, Bratislava.

TK15 Visioning. The task presumes creation and presentation of a strong common vision for particular area, around which it would be possible to build a regeneration strategy.

TK 16 Conceptual model design (the task might be placed under the LA72)

LA72 – Design - Habitat Regeneration Action

This learning activity is intended to be a set of various learning tasks within which students present the design process or proposed actions as part of a regeneration strategy for a selected area.

TK20 Presentation of the design/action

1. Sequence of tasks

LA 69 The Workspace intro	TK4 Introduce yourself and explain your reasons for choosing this course and expectations from international collaboration.	TK5 Group introduction.							
LA70 Urban Habitat Regeneration and Integrative Urban Design in Sustainable Development			TK6 Exploring the case of Ciutat Vella, Barcelona	TK8 Exploring examples of urban regeneration strategies					
LA71 Regeneration Strategies for selected area					TK9 Habitat analyses	TK10 Urban morphology and regeneration of riverbanks	TK11 Urban mobility	TK15 Process of visioning	TK16 Conceptual model design
LA72 Design – Habitat regeneration action									TK20 Presentation of the action / design
Timing									
	Sept 2014	Sept 2014	Oct 2014	Oct 2014	Nov 2014	Nov 2014	Nov 2014	Dec 2014	Dec 2014 /Jan, Feb 2015
AF_Belgrade	TK4	X	TK6	TK8	TK9	X	X	TK15	TK20
FASTU	TK4	TK5	TK6	TK8	TK9	X	TK11	X	TK16
VSUACE	X	TK5	X	X	TK9	X	X	X	TK16
UPMF						TK10			

Not all tasks have to be done by all partners; partners not participating in a specific Task can put an X in the table above instead of a date.

10. Define ways of collaboration / collaboration levels:

(e.g. Cross-Institutional, Trans-Institutional, Link to other WPs)

- Exchange of information relevant for the topics
- Widen understanding of needs for habitat regeneration in different European countries
- Share and record video-lectures
- Organize videoconference critiques and presentations

11. In addition to the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus tools (WS, Case Repository) what other collaboration tools / environments are you using? What for?

A Facebook Group at: <https://www.facebook.com/groups/716510478414701/> has been established as an additional communication channel for less formal exchange of relevant information.

The teachers are in daily contact via Gmail chat channel and the Facebook chat.

12. What are your expectations regarding the impact / influence of using the collaborative learning space.

AF Belgrade (P26)

For you as a teacher?

- To compare the proposed collaborative learning space with the other similar environments used previously.
- To efficiently coordinate the teaching/learning process.

For your students?

- The students are expected to be more motivated, since they learn in an international context.
- The opportunity to learn from international experts.

For your course?

- The course has been created exclusively for this cooperation. It is a “vertical” elective, offered to third and fifth year students. We expect them to accomplish some group tasks, working in mixed (maybe international) groups...

For your institution?

- An opportunity to compare teaching methodologies and to develop new ones.

FASTU (P3)

For you as a teacher?

- Research on the topic of urban regeneration strategies in European scale

For your students?

- Working in international learning environment, integration of participative methods

For your course?

- Acknowledgement with the new methods of teaching and learning

For your institution?

- Wide collaboration with European and world institutions and partners, new partnerships and friendships

FAVSUACE (P31)

For you as a teacher?

- To study foreign methods of the teaching and learning
- To expand boundaries of interaction.
- Working out of models of habitat regeneration is expected too.

For your students?

- The students are expected of working in groups with international experts

For your course?

- Working out of models of habitat regeneration is expected

For your institution?

- VSUACE is expected for creation of a joint advisory group of teachers

IUG Grenoble (P18)

For you as a teacher?

- Collaborate with teachers from WP4, exchange documentation allowing studying European cities in a comparative way

For your students?

- Collaborating with students from other countries

For your course?

- Giving the course an international dimension by studying cities from Central and Eastern Europe and benefitting from the expertise of colleagues from CEE countries

For your institution?

- Experiment introducing OIKONET in the teaching process at IUG

13) Please check the project goals to which your learning space will contribute:

Promoting cooperation between research, education and society , by bringing together stakeholders from different areas to formulate and discuss contemporary problems regarding housing at a European and global scale.	x
Providing students, teachers, researchers and other stakeholders with the competences necessary to work in a readily accessible international environment	x
Encouraging the active participation of these stakeholders in the creation of innovative learning spaces which overcome disciplinary and institutional boundaries	x
Facilitating cooperation between different academic programs which include housing (in its different dimensions) as subject matter.	•
Fostering physical and virtual mobility across partner institutions, by means of workshops, seminars, conferences and shared learning activities in blended learning scenarios dedicated to study contemporary housing issues.	x
Contributing to the internationalisation of the European cooperation , incorporating third countries to the network. This will facilitate the exchange and mobility at the international level, preparing the ground for further cooperation among network partners in future programs (Erasmus Mundus).	x
Promoting new forms of international cooperation , through the design and implementation of shared learning activities carried out following a blended learning approach with the digital environments of the OIKODOMOS virtual campus.	x
Establishing evaluation procedures to guarantee the quality of the pedagogic activities to be implemented by network partners, in mixed formal and informal pedagogical settings.	
Establishing evaluation procedures to guarantee the quality of the pedagogic activities to be implemented by network partners, in mixed formal and informal pedagogical settings.	
Reinforcing the societal roles of academic institutions in a culturally and linguistically diverse Europe, by embedding the learning activities in those social milieus in which solutions for housing problems are needed (integration, immigration) thus activating knowledge through interaction with society.	x
Enhancing interdisciplinarity and transdisciplinarity , by creating new learning spaces which bring together different disciplines into the solution of housing problems.	x
Contributing to the development of technology enhanced learning , embedding ICT in the learning processes and learning structures.	x

8.3 APPENDIX C. Learning plan: Threshold Matters

1. Theme

Threshold Matters

2. Description

In a high-density world the relation between the private sphere and the public sphere is of an utmost importance. The way dwellings relate to the public sphere is one of the paramount issues designers deal with in their practise.

In this workspace students will ‘designerly’ research the relation between the domain of the dwelling and the domain of the public. The work in this workspace focuses on the intersection and overlay spaces of the public realm and the private sphere.

The students will explore the relation of the (private) dwelling to the (public) street and vice versa. In doing so they will research how this relation can be seen as a field of mutual influence.

The learning activities in this workspace will be both of a theoretical and designerly nature, working on specific case studies and design assignments.

3. Course Level(s)

- KUL (P4): Master Students through elective course OIKONET
- GTU (P13): Bachelor students / second year, Design Studio, must course
- BUT (P27): Master students / 1st year, design Studio, elective course – *second semester*
- DIT (P29): No students in 1st semester, teacher involvement
- ETSA-UPV (P2): Master students./ 1st year, design Studio, elective course

4. Coordinator

- Sedef Özçelik Güney/ GTU, Turkey (P13)
- Tomas Ooms / Faculty of Architecture KU Leuven, Belgium (P4)

5. Participating Partners

- Aleksander Asanowicz, Katarzyna Asanowicz, Adam Jakimowicz, Bialystok University of Technology, Faculty of Architecture (P27)
- Jim Roche, Dublin Institute of Technology (P29)
- Carla Sentieri, School of Architecture, Universidad Politécnica de Valencia (P2)

6. Learning objectives

General aim of the workspace

Through the production of a series of sections and other drawings students aim to understand the concept of ‘Threshold Matters’, the zone that makes the relation from the private sphere to the public sphere. Through the drawings students will map the characteristics of this relation and probe for common ground between the concern of private space and the concern of public space. The drawings should enable students to designerly take a stance on the current issue of public/private and how architecture facilitates the movement from one sphere to the other and on how the private relates to the public and vice versa. But it also investigates the possibility of communication both existing and newly imagined. This could lead to a description of a desired relation and an architectural expression of this.

Specific learning outcomes

- The student is able to reflect on contemporary and innovative architectural-theoretical perspectives (KUL P4), (ETSA-UPV P2), (BUT P27);
- The student is able to communicate his/her research from a artistic-architectural perspective in a visual and verbal way (KUL P4), (ETSA-UPV P2), (BUT P27);
- The student is able to think and act across cultures (KUL P4), (ETSA-UPV P2), (BUT P27);
- The student will be able to research necessary resources related with the architectural design process, and explore formally and conceptually relevant examples for the

design issue, and make use of all these research products in the design process (GTU P13), (ETSA-UPV P2);

- The student will be able to present their architectural ideas and designs both visually and verbally since all the exercises performed in the studio will be open to discussion and sharing (GTU P13), (BUT P27);
- The student will be able to develop an awareness for various processes shaping architecture (GTU P13);
- The students will be able to gain the ability of critical thinking on problems related with architecture a social discipline (GTU P13), (ETSA-UPV P2);

7. Partners contributions

KUL (P4)

- Specific expertise: design studio, research on public-private interface
- Teaching and learning resources (e.g. Online or other formats): elective OIKONET course as a assessment activities:
- Past experiences / courses:
- What is your contribution / job in creating the learning space: coordinator and teacher

GTU (P13)

- Specific expertise: design studio, research on public-private interface
- Teaching and learning resources (e.g. Online or other formats): design studio on housing
- Assessment activities: commenting on the other partners' inputs, critiques can be given online other partners' studios
- Past experiences / courses: design studio teaching on housing and public venues in the housing circles, teaching experience of OIKODOMOS project (2011)
- What is your contribution / job in creating the learning space: coordinator and teacher

BUT (P27)

- Specific expertise: Design studio, explorative digital media usage in design
- Teaching and learning resources (e.g. Online or other formats): Experimental Design Studio + online resources
- Assessment activities: discussions in a group, online comments from partner institutions possible
- Past experiences / courses: Experimental Design Studio (Blurred Function Space)
- What is your contribution / job in creating the Learning Space: coordinator and teacher: teacher

DIT (P29)

- Specific expertise:
- Teaching and learning resources (e.g. Online or other formats):
- Assessment activities:
- Past experiences / courses:

- What is your contribution / job in creating the learning space: teacher

ETSA-UPV (P2)

- Specific expertise: design studio, research on public-private interface
- Teaching and learning resources (e.g. Online or other formats): design studio on housing + online resources
- Assessment activities: discussions in a group, online comments from partner institutions
- Past experiences / courses: design studio teaching on housing and sustainability
- What is your contribution / job in creating the learning space: teacher

8. Learning Activities

“Threshold Matters” will be implemented in three courses: The OIKONET Elective Course for Master students at KUL, the GTU second year bachelor Design Studio and the in collaboration with students of the Second year Grade Architecture. Master students from ETSA-UPV. The topic of Threshold Matters will thus be tackled in different context and in different ways. Each course has a different track and sequence of tasks. They all participate in the same Learning Activities but will have their own specific sequence of Tasks. Some tasks will be done collectively, others will build on the work the other courses have produced. Within the context of the learning design it is to be noted that ad hoc tasks can be added to the sequence.

The activities started in the spring semester of 2014 at the beginning of the OIKONET project. Partners from GTU, KUL, DIT and BUT agreed to develop and collaborate around the topic of Thresholds. A first version, or ‘run’, was set in motion in the fall semester of 2014. A second more profound and integrated version will be active during the fall semester of 2014/2015. It is for that version that this template is created. However we decided to keep the task from the first version listed in this document. For each task description we will indicate in what semester it was active. The general structure of the Threshold Matters Workspace was kept identical only the learning activity LA A MICRO PERSPECTIVE: THE “CASE STUDY” was added.

What follows here is an abstract of each of the courses describing the context and the way the different LA and TK are involved.

OIKONET Elective (KUL)

The OIKONET elective is an International Housing Research Lab. The lab works within a network of 34 universities and institutions. The aim of OIKONET is to create a platform of international collaboration to study contemporary housing. The multiple dimensions of dwelling in today’s societies: architectural, urban, environmental, economic, cultural and social are explored from a multidisciplinary and global perspective.

"Space is inherent in a plan but visual in a section". We will use the section to study and develop these contemporary housing issues. The section is a powerful design and research tool. We will explore the multiple interpretations of a section and we will do so on different scales: from the urban section to the detail section.

The elective will be organised as a design seminar based on interaction and collaboration between different architectural students from all over Europe and beyond. The elective is linked to an international workshop and an international conference.

The students will participate in Learning Activities 56, 57 and 58. The sequence of task is:

- TK6 Getting to know the OIKODOMOS platform
- TK7 #Threshold Matters
- TK8 Threshold in Parallel
- TK9 Architectural Review
- TK10 Urban CT scanning
- TK11 Urban CT Scanning written to graphical
- TK12 Design assignment: A Moment Between U & I

GTU Design Studio

The GTU design studio applies a “folded design teaching” method that is constituted in order to solidify the abstract notions that come along with the notion of “house” and “thresholds”. This particular method will divide the semester into three fragments:

01. Experimental teaching – Parallel Studios: space impact Episodes, Conceptual mappings _ Architectural Expressions This is linked to the **LA56 Explorations upon concepts of Threshold Matters**. The following tasks will be involved:

- TK1 Visual Impulses (will be exercised for a second time)
- TK6 Getting to know the OIKODOMOS platform
- TK7 #Threshold Matters
- TK8 threshold in parallel: trans-edges/thresholds

02. Focus on in-situ – Parallel visions: Exercises on case studies

The particular case study will be implemented to the design studio exercise in order to make full comprehension for the problems put forward. This will be developed through **LA 57 Urban CT Scanning / Urban Tomography working on TK11 Urban CT Scanning** written to graphical / Connected to **TK7**.

03. Design interventions – micro scale design proposals

Seeks for design proposals and innovative solutions with respect to the housing design problem and notions studied. **LA 58 A micro perspective towards the “case study” neighbourhood / design will be the working context working on TK13 HOUSING/micro perspective: “Lonely man’s shelter”**.

ETSA_UPV

The ETSA_UPV design studio is called: “RECYCLING OF THE PUBLIC SPACE AND URBAN DESIGN and is a subject belonging to the Line of Specialization 2, ARCHITECTURE AND SUSTAINABLE HABITAT, of the MÁSTER IN ADVANCED ARCHITECTURE, LANDSCAPE, URBANISM AND DESIGN (MAAPUD) of València's Universitat Politècnica. It take place during the first semester: November and December.

The concept in general could be easily adapted to the urban contexts and the overall need to explore relations between public and private aspects of dwelling.

Students from ETSA_UPV will participate in Learning Activities LA56, LA57, in the following tasks:

- TK1 Visual Impulses
- TK7 #Threshold Matters
- TK9 Architectural Review
- TK10 Urban Tc Scanning
- TK12 Design assignment: A Moment Between U & I
-

BUT Design Studio

The BUT design studio developed within OIKONET scheme is based on the previously developed Experimental Design Studio within which the concepts of the Blurred Function Space were conceived by the students. The concept in general could be easily adapted to the urban contexts and the overall need to explore relations between public and private aspects of dwelling.

Within the approach the following stages can be distinguished:

1. Searching

- Developing understanding of the design task
- Finding Inspirations
- Initial Idea Searching

2. Questioning

- Dealing with constraints
- Defining questions relevant to the design task

3. Creating

- Ideas developing
- Designing Process

The three above stages are structured so that the local as well as the collaborative evaluations are possible.

Students from BUT will work within Learning Activities LA 56, LA57 collaborate in performing the following tasks:

- TK1 Visual Impulses
- TK7 #Threshold Matters
- TK9 Architectural Review

In the following section the LA's and Task are described. There are three LA's: LA56 Explorations upon concepts of Threshold Matters, LA57 Urban CT Scanning / Urban Tomography and LA58 A micro perspective: the "case study".

LA56 EXPLORATIONS OF CONCEPTS

- Description

This particular Learning Activity seeks to explore the following concepts with respect to the architectural expression of the philosophical background of these concepts:

- Soft edges
- Homogeneity
- Heterogeneity
- Sense of belonging
- Formation of identity
- Hierarchy of space Private to Public
- Liveliness
- Affordances
- Privacy vs. territoriality
- Types of permanent migration
- Ambiguity of space; private/public versus public/private
- Treatment of surfaces and detailing in the threshold zone
- Opportunities for socialising
- Threshold
- Common space
- Dual space
- Collective

- Keywords

Knowledge Mining; Thresholds; Spatial and Social Patterns; Interfaces

- Learning Outcomes

- The student will be able to develop an awareness for various processes shaping architecture (GTU P13);
- The students will be able to gain the ability of critical thinking on problems related with architecture a social discipline (GTU P13);

- Task 1 Visual Impulses

The goal of this task is to clarify the concepts that make reference to the phenomena of “Threshold” in the urban context. This first task aims to enhance the understanding of the concept of “Threshold Matters” and provide a general approach towards the idea of ‘threshold spaces’. Visual material is urged for this conceptual mining work to comprehend the abstract concepts. Moreover this task aims to provide a visual archive for the concepts for students in their future studies in this particular workspace activities.

These concepts (see above LA56) that relate to the idea of threshold in the urban context make reference to the formulation of space: Each concept mentioned above is going to be presented via one particular image within an A3 (max. 2MB) document that is graphically designed. The images should be chosen carefully in order to make thorough understanding of the “urban threshold” phenomena.

Students and teachers from ETSA-UPV will comment on the results of this task.

Participating courses: GTU, ETSA- UPV

Active: spring semester 2013/2014 and fall semester 2014/2015

- Task 4. Texture, Detail and Representation

Threshold is ambiguous. That zone in architecture between the public and private worlds is hardly ever defined strictly but instead has many layers and associated treatments. The boundaries that legally define property for example do not define visual privacy. It has varied meanings and treatments across different cultures and climates. Threshold is an ambiguous zone often described in planning terms as ‘public/private’ or ‘private/public’, a zone that affords options for socializing and amenity, a place to meet neighbours and for children to play. In housing it is a transition between the very public realm of the street and the very private world of the dwelling. A consideration of its detail treatment is vital in defining an attitude to threshold. These concepts below give clues regarding threshold in the urban context and how it might contribute to the formulation of space: Soft / hard edges Homogeneity Heterogeneity Sense of belonging Formation of identity Liveliness Affordances Opportunities for socialising Privacy vs. territoriality Types of permanent migration Hierarchy of space - Private and Public Ambiguity of space: private/public vs. public/private. The task is for students to clarify their intentions for the detail treatment of a threshold space in their timber housing project. This could be an entrance from the street, a courtyard, an access gallery, a staircase or a hallway. Or part of any of these and other spaces. Each student should develop one or more drawings showing this treatment. These could be an atmospheric 3-d drawing or a 1:10 detailed section or a combination of varied drawings. This exercise may overlap with your BTS study. You should then upload the drawing/s, along with a short descriptive text (no more than 100 words) and an overall drawing or two of your scheme (overall 3-d, section and/or floor plan), to the ‘Threshold Matters’ Workspace on the OIKONET website. You are encouraged to comment on or query other students’ work on the workspace. Each student’s work will be part of a visual resource archive shared by students in schools of architecture from Turkey, Belgium and Poland who are also part of this workspace. But many others who access the OIKONET website will also be able to view your work.

This task ran in AC 2013-2014 and will not be part of the current focus of the workspace.

Since the task exists in the pl
 Participating courses: DIT,
 Active: spring semester 2013/2014

- Task 5 Blurred Function Space

Developing the concepts of interrelation between private and public spaces in the given urban context.

This task ran in AC 2013-2014 and will not be part of the current focus of the workspace. Since the task exists in the platform, the description and task number remain part of this document.

Participating courses: BUT,
 Active: spring semester 2013/2014

- Task 6 Getting to know the OIKODOMOS platform

Browse through the OIKODOMOS workspaces (Civic Housing, Introduction to Housing and the Contemporary Living Patterns workspaces) and select a work that has been uploaded. Try to understand the work and write a short comment on the work. The comment should be constructive and address both the content of the work and the way it is communicated on the OIKODOMOS platform.

The task is done by all students. The task of the teachers is to enhance communication between the students of the different courses.

Participating courses: GTU, KUL
 Active: fall semester 2014/2015

- Task 7 #Threshold Matters

Select 4 (four) of the concepts mentioned in the description of LA56 Explorations upon concepts of Threshold Matters and write a 140 character message per concept through which you show your understanding and interpreting of that concept. If you could link this to a current actual debate (news in general or architectural in specific) this would be a plus.

The messages that are written by KUL students (4 of the concepts mentioned in the description of LA56 Explorations upon concepts of Threshold Matters) will be discussed by GTU students using 25 words comments. A comparison between the discussions in the GTU Studio and how KUL Students cover the issues will be tackled in the comments.

ETSA-UPV students will read the description and look for a new text (from the theory of architecture) to complement it. Make a constructive comment.

Participating courses: GTU, KUL, ETSA-UPV
 Active: fall semester 2014/2015

- Task 8 threshold in parallel: trans-edges/thresholds

The input for the Parallel Studios: space impact Episodes will be formulated as A3 posters. The dis/continuity between the ground/wall/canopy elements will be explored relating these thresholds with the feelings of cold/soaked/dirty/thirsty/tired.

KUL students will formulate a short comment on the work.

Participating courses: GTU, KUL, ETSA-UPV
 Active: fall semester 2014/2015

Task 9 Architectural Review

Using the OIKODOMOS Case Repository select an architectural project that relates to the topics you discussed and propose a graphic review on how the project relates to the concept (select four projects and produce four A3's).

ETSA-UPV Students must look for another project that relates to the same topic and give the reference to the student. It can be a way to put in relation the students.

Participating courses: KUL, ETSA-UPV

Active: fall semester 2014/2015

LA URBAN CT SCANNING / URBAN TOMOGRAPHY

- Description

This particular Learning Activity seeks for **CT Scans of the urban realm within** housing settlements and/or detail studies of threshold spaces on particular project sites with respect to the architectural expression of the philosophical background of the concepts that were explored in LA 56 Exploration upon concepts of Threshold Matters.

The concept of the CT scan is an analogical reference to Urban Tomography; where **Tomography** is a definition for imaging by sections or sectioning.

Through the production of a series of sections and other drawings students aim to understand the Threshold Matters, the zone that makes the relation from the private sphere to the public sphere. Through the drawings students will map the characteristics of this relation and probe for common ground between the concern of private space and the concern of public space. The drawings should enable students to designerly take a stance on the current issue of public/private and how architecture facilitates the movement from one sphere to the other and on how the private relates to the public and vice versa. But it also investigates the possibility of communication both existing and newly imagined. This could lead to a description of a desired relation and an architectural expression of this.

- Keywords

Mapping; Boundaries; Thresholds; Urban Analysis

- Learning Outcomes

- The student will be able to research necessary resources related with the architectural design process, and explore formally and conceptually relevant examples for the design issue, and make use of all these research products in the design process (GTU P13);
- The student will be able to present their architectural ideas and designs both visually and verbally since all the exercises performed in the studio will be open to discussion and sharing (GTU P13);

- Task 2 Find and explore further techniques for scanning in order to describe the case study

- Task 3 Content of the “threshold” Study of the Project area (GTU P13)

- Task 10 Urban CT Scanning / Urban Tomography

Produce a series of sections on the (proposed/given/selected) site. The sections should

address and highlight the Threshold Matter on an urban level.

Students from ETSA-UPV will follow the process and make comments on the works.

Participating courses: KUL, ETSA-UPV
Active: fall semester 2014/2015

- Task 11 Urban CT Scanning written to graphical (Connected to TK7)

A series of sections will be produced in the CT manner regarding the concepts that are tackled by KUL students at TK 7. A3 posters will be designed for the case study area: Uskudar/Istanbul. Every GTU student participating will select a KUL student's paper and produce the tomography work regarding the written essay by this particular student.

Students from KUL will follow the process and possibly can respond to questions / act as mentors for the GTU students.

Participating courses: GTU, KUL
Active: fall semester 2014/2015

LA A MICRO PERSPECTIVE: THE “CASE STUDY”

- Task 12 Design assignment: A Moment Between U & I

Question our contemporary way of relating projects to the public domain. Through the use of sections you need to build up a design that relates to the research track that you followed by completing the previous tasks. The output is a section model of undefined length but the width is 1,00m (on scale of 1/50). The section is a reflection on Threshold Matters.

Students from ETSA-UPV will follow the process and make comments on the works.

Participating courses: KUL, ETSA-UPV
Active: fall semester 2014/2015

- Task 13 HOUSING/micro perspective: “Lonely man’s shelter”

Design interventions will be made through the programme of “Lonely man’s shelter” who seeks for thresholds to interact in the everyday life of Uskudar. Keeping in mind the saying by Jon Bon Jovi: “No man is an island”, every users looks for some interaction around dwelling space that brings about the question of Thresholds with such potentials. The design solutions are required for a single-living person trying to make connections with the physical and social surroundings of Uskudar. A2 Poster, design proposals are reflected with the conceptual approaches. Scale; 1/500, 1/100.

Participating courses: GTU
Active: fall semester 2014/2015

2. Define Sequence of Tasks (which is prerequisite)

LA56	TK1			TK4	TK5	TK6	TK7	TK8	TK9				
LA57		TK2	TK3							TK10	TK11		
LA58												TK12	TK13
LAXX													
Timing													
KUL (P4)	X	X	X	X	X	03/101 7/10	03/10 17/10	15/11 25/11	10/10 31/10	24/10 21/11	25/11 30/11	17/11 19/12	X
GTU(P 13)	19/09 23/09	X	X	X	X	12/10 15/10	15/10 25/10	10/11 15/11	X	X	25/11 30/11	X	11/12 15/12
ETSA-UPV (P2)	30/09 17/10						28/10 7/11		10/11 17/11	24/11 2/12		12/12 22/12	
BUT (P27)	03 - 2015	X	X	X	X	X	05 - 2015	X	06 - 2015	X	X	X	X

Not all tasks have to be done by all partners, partners not participating in a specific Task can put an X in the table above instead of a date.

10. Define ways of collaboration / collaboration levels:
(e.g. Cross-Institutional, Trans-Institutional, Link to other WPs)

The way in which this is to be done and integrated in this workspace is mentioned in the task descriptions and on the planning document.

11- In addition to the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus tools (WS, Case Repository) what other collaboration tools / environments are you using? What for?

Tools used by all participants: OIKONET platform, Facebook, Dropbox, OIKODOMOS case repository.

12- What are your expectations regarding the impact / influence of using the in the collaborative learning space.

KUL (P4)

- For you as a teacher: international experience at home, collaboration with colleagues, experience learning design, broadening of understanding of the topic;
- For your students: international experience at home, broadening of understanding of the topic;
- For your course: a smashing success... ;-)
- For your institution:

GTU (P13)

- For you as a teacher: sharing new methodologies for studio teaching, monitoring different levels of students
- For your students: experiencing an international platform, comprehension of international perspectives towards their work
- For your course: enrichment of the curriculum via variety of teaching tools
- For your institution: an international perspective and data teaching data sharing

BUT (P27)

- For you as a teacher: exploring new design methods, widening the understanding of new possible approaches to urban spaces
- For your students: international experience at home, developing the ability to critical thinking in design
- For your course: enrichment of the curriculum thanks to the new design methods involved and new types of design outcomes
- For your institution: widening the perspective of teaching / learning possibilities

DIT (P29)

- For you as a teacher: curious about how the interactions will give insight into teaching of housing, opens up a sharing collaborative non-combative space
- For your students: allows them to interact easily with fellow students abroad and to observe and comment on works in a professional manner which should enrich their learning and broaden their horizon
- For your course: enriches and internationalises the course
- For your institution: connects it internationally, broadens its profile

ETS-UPV (P2)

- For you as a teacher: sharing new methodologies for studio teaching, monitoring different levels of students
- For your students: experiencing an international platform, comprehension of international perspectives towards their work

- For your course: enrichment of the curriculum via variety of teaching tools
- For your institution: an international perspective and data teaching data sharing

13) Please check the project goals to which your learning space will contribute:

Promoting cooperation between research, education and society , by bringing together stakeholders from different areas to formulate and discuss contemporary problems regarding housing at a European and global scale.	x
Providing students, teachers, researchers and other stakeholders with the competences necessary to work in a readily accessible international environment	x
Encouraging the active participation of these stakeholders in the creation of innovative learning spaces which overcome disciplinary and institutional boundaries	x
Facilitating cooperation between different academic programs which include housing (in its different dimensions) as subject matter.	x
Fostering physical and virtual mobility across partner institutions, by means of workshops, seminars, conferences and shared learning activities in blended learning scenarios dedicated to study contemporary housing issues.	x
Contributing to the internationalisation of the European cooperation , incorporating third countries to the network. This will facilitate the exchange and mobility at the international level, preparing the ground for further cooperation among network partners in future programs (Erasmus Mundus).	x
Promoting new forms of international cooperation , through the design and implementation of shared learning activities carried out following a blended learning approach with the digital environments of the OIKODOMOS virtual campus.	x
Establishing evaluation procedures to guarantee the quality of the pedagogic activities to be implemented by network partners, in mixed formal and informal pedagogical settings.	x
Establishing evaluation procedures to guarantee the quality of the pedagogic activities to be implemented by network partners, in mixed formal and informal pedagogical settings.	x
Reinforcing the societal roles of academic institutions in a culturally and linguistically diverse Europe, by embedding the learning activities in those social milieus in which solutions for housing problems are needed (integration, immigration) thus activating knowledge through interaction with society.	
Enhancing interdisciplinarity and transdisciplinarity , by creating new learning spaces which bring together different disciplines into the solution of housing problems.	x
Contributing to the development of technology enhanced learning , embedding ICT in the learning processes and learning structures.	x

8.4 APPENDIX D. Learning plan: Housing Systems

1. Theme

Housing Systems

2. Description

The purpose of the seminar is to introduce the concept of housing system. Understanding housing as a system means to take into consideration –all at once–: 1. the components that make a particular system (not only the physical elements such as structural components, but also the dwellers that inhabit the spaces) and 2. the interactions between the components (between structural components and building envelope, between dwellers and spaces). This notion of housing as system can be traced back to the work of Habraken and the SAR group in the 1960-70s. Nowadays, the notion of system pervades in the Open Building movement.

Understanding housing as system implies dealing with issues such as industrialization and fabrication (mass customization), dwellers' participation, and adaptability. The application of ICT to the housing generation enables to address generative modelling (rule-based systems, parametric design).

3. Course level(s)

- Students from 3rd, 4th and 5th year of the 5 year architectural program.
- Preferably for students of the upper courses; ideally Master students.

4. Coordinator

Leandro Madrazo, School of Architecture La Salle

5. Participating partners

Nadia Charalambous, Department of Architecture, University of Cyprus (P15)

6. Learning objectives

- *General aim of the learning space*

The general aim of the learning space is to introduce a different perspective for housing design, changing the paradigm from the design of an object to the design of a system. The pedagogic purpose of this approach is to develop design strategies that enable to encompass the multiples dimensions determining the design of a living place, from social or psychological aspects to construction or economics factors.

- *Specific learning outcomes*

- to understand the basic principle of designing a housing system: that housing is a system (physical and abstract) made of sub-systems which are interrelated.
- to be confronted to the task of building a model of housing system
- to learn to play the role of “system designer” rather than designer of “a building”

- to be aware that system design implies the participation of multiple stakeholders (including dwellers), and that the system should enable them taking decisions in their respective decision making realm.

7. Partners contribution

La Salle (P1)

Expertise: The expertise comes from developing the BARCODE HOUSING SYSTEM from 2002 to 2009.

Teaching and learning resources (e.g. online or other formats): The BARCODE HOUSING system developed by our research group will serve as a model and example. The underlying principles of the system will be explained, its generative rules explained. Then, students will be asked to generate "solutions" within this system. We will use the Case Repository in the first part of the seminar. We will use Workspaces to carry out the tasks of the second part of the seminar.

Assessment activities: They will focus mostly on practical works

Past experiences / courses: We have not done a seminar on the topic of housing systems yet, this will be the first time we do so.

What is your contribution / job in creating the Learning Space: We have proposed the topic, and create the Learning Structure (Activities and Tasks).

UCY (P15)

Specific expertise: relevant design and research work through the housing studio taught at UCY since 2008.

Teaching and learning resources (e.g. online or other formats) studio blog and postgraduate course blog (includes all learning material).

Assessment activities and feedback; analysis of precedents and examples. joint assessment and feedback through sharing of our assessment tools.

Past experiences / courses taught at UCY; we do not have a similar seminar but a design studio on housing which includes theoretical work as well.

8. Learning Activities

LA1: UNDERSTANDING HOUSING TYPES

- Description

Identifying types of housing according to some specific criteria (the built-in taxonomy of the case repository).

- Keywords

Type, typology

- Learning outcomes

- Develop an understanding of the multiple and complex variables in relation to context that influence existing and new proposal
- The student will be able to analyse the multiple variables that influence existing housing designs
- The student will be able to make appropriate use of different representation techniques (verbally, texturally and graphic-digital and analogue) in order to communicate their ideas (concepts and design proposals) in an effective manner.
- The student will conduct research on housing topics and apply the information in new contexts.
- The student will be able to define the issues affecting the actual design of residential architecture (following the new social structures, globalisation, materials...)
- The student will be able to show an understanding of the different construction systems (concrete, steel frame, wood frame, etc.) and is able to integrate them properly in a design proposal.

- Task 1 Creating a housing collection

Identify and group housing case studies according to some specific criteria. These criteria, based on the built-in taxonomy of the case repository, will be representative of contemporary domestic architecture.

- Task 2 Creating a housing case study

To search for a new case study of housing to be included into OIKDOMOS Case Repository. The new case study must fulfil some of the criteria chosen on Task 1 by the student. These criteria, based on the built-in taxonomy of the case repository, will be representative of contemporary domestic architecture.

- Task 3 Reflecting on housing types

To summarize in a short essay -2 pages maximum, without figures- some notion of type or typology derived from the readings. The essay should comply with academic conventions concerning quotations and use of bibliographic references.

LA2: INTRODUCING HOUSING SYSTEMS

- Description

To introduce the basic concepts, based on theoretical precedents (e.g. Habraken's theories, Open Building)

- Keywords

System, support and infill

- Learning outcomes

- Develop an understanding of the multiple and complex variables in relation to context that influence existing and new proposal
- The student will be able to make appropriate use of different representation techniques (verbally, texturally and graphic-digital and analogue) in order to communicate their ideas (concepts and design proposals) in an effective manner.
- The student will conduct research on housing topics and apply the information in new contexts.

- The student will be able to critique their own work and that of others by reference to established models of good practice and the appropriate standards

- Task 4. Critical reading of selected essays

The activity consisted in writing a short essay summarizing the concept of system in architecture, based on the reading of selected texts from John Habraken Christopher Alexander, the Team X and the Open Building group.

- Task 5. Study of precedents

The task is to analyse and present different previous works which the idea of system is present (mat buildings, etc...)

Task 6_ Understanding BCHS

Introduction to the BARCODE HOUSING SYSTEM (BCHS). The tasks is to understand the structure and the performance of the BCHS to create new housing schemes based on it.

LA3: DEVISING HOUSING SYSTEMS

- Description

Generating housing designs within a housing system

- Keywords

Generative design, rule-based systems

- Learning outcomes

- Develop an understanding of the multiple and complex variables in relation to context that influence existing and new proposal
- The student will be able to make appropriate use of different representation techniques (verbally, texturally and graphic-digital and analogue) in order to communicate their ideas(concepts and design proposals) in an effective manner.
- The student will conduct research on housing topics and apply the information in new contexts.
- The student will be able to critique their own work and that of others by reference to established models of good practice and the appropriate standards

- Task 7 Devising a housing system

The students propose a housing system, designing its internal structure and its performance, in a way that it would be able to generate different housing solutions for diriment inputs (contexts, programs, etc)

- Task 8 Generating designs within the proposed system

The students propose housing designs within their own designed housing system

9. Sequence of tasks

TASKS								
	Oct.	Oct.	Oct.	Nov.	Nov.	Nov.	Dec.	Jan.

LA1	TK1	TK2	TK3					
LA2				TK4	Tk5	TK6		
LA3							TK7	TK8
LA4								

10. Define ways of collaboration / collaboration levels:

(e.g. Cross-Institutional, Trans-Institutional, Link to other WPs)

- Cross-institutional. Some concrete tasks can be shared with courses at other institutions, for instance:

- Specific tasks can be shared with other partners
- Student works can be commented by teachers or students from other institutions
- Lectures by teleconference on specific themes: housing types, housing systems, BARCODE HOUSING SYSTEM

Other partners can propose video lectures on related themes.

-Links to other WPs. The relationship with other WPs will focus on the research category “DESIGN (Methods, Concepts, Applications in Architecture and Spatial Planning)” defined in the matrix. In particular, WP2 Research partners can participate by:

- Suggesting bibliography and case studies
- Commenting some of the student works, particularly essays

9. In addition to the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus tools (WS, Case Repository) what other collaboration tools / environments are you using? What for?

We will use OIKODOMOS Case Repository and Workspaces. A Twitter channel has been created (@Housing_Systems). Besides, we want to facilitate discussions about select topics in more “social” environments; it could be a Facebook page or a blog.

Some of the material produced (e.g. explanations of the BARCODE HOUSING SYSTEM) could be useful for the MOOC.

10. What are your expectations regarding the impact / influence of using the in the collaborative learning space.

La Salle (P1)

For you as a teacher?

- This is the first time we put together a seminar on the topic of Housing Systems. It will help us to bring to students the expertise we gained in the creation of the BARCODE HOUSING SYSTEMS. It will help us to disseminate the results of this project among the consortium.

For your students?

- Students are typically asked to design specific design solutions for a particular site, program, etc. Rarely they are confronted to the task of designing a “system”.

For your course?

- It will open up a new line of work not explored until now, if possible engaging other partners in it

For your institution?

- It will help to create ties between research and pedagogic activities, an issue which is not always easy to tackle.

- *Institution_UCY (P15)*

For you as a teacher?

- To incorporate blended learning in my teaching
- To get feedback from colleagues in different academic environments
- To get familiar with different and diverse teaching methods and learning resources

For your students?

- They will be exposed to different cultural and academic contexts
- They will be able to experience different methods of learning through the virtual campus
- They will have the opportunity to comment on other students’ work but also receive feedback from both peers and tutors

For your course?

- It will be enriched both in terms of teaching methodology but also in terms of references and learning resources
- It will gain from constructive criticism from both students and colleagues abroad

For your institution?

- To enhance the possibilities for international networking and collaboration
- To increase students and staff exchanges

13) Please check the project goals to which your learning space will contribute:

Promoting cooperation between research, education and society , by bringing together stakeholders from different areas to formulate and discuss contemporary problems regarding housing at a European and global scale.	
Providing students, teachers, researchers and other stakeholders with the competences necessary to work in a readily accessible international environment	x
Encouraging the active participation of these stakeholders in the creation of innovative learning spaces which overcome disciplinary and institutional boundaries	x
Facilitating cooperation between different academic programs which include housing (in its different dimensions) as subject matter.	x
Fostering physical and virtual mobility across partner institutions, by means of workshops, seminars,	

conferences and shared learning activities in blended learning scenarios dedicated to study contemporary housing issues.	
Contributing to the internationalisation of the European cooperation , incorporating third countries to the network. This will facilitate the exchange and mobility at the international level, preparing the ground for further cooperation among network partners in future programs (Erasmus Mundus).	x
Promoting new forms of international cooperation , through the design and implementation of shared learning activities carried out following a blended learning approach with the digital environments of the OIKODOMOS virtual campus.	x
Establishing evaluation procedures to guarantee the quality of the pedagogic activities to be implemented by network partners, in mixed formal and informal pedagogical settings.	
Establishing evaluation procedures to guarantee the quality of the pedagogic activities to be implemented by network partners, in mixed formal and informal pedagogical settings.	x
Reinforcing the societal roles of academic institutions in a culturally and linguistically diverse Europe, by embedding the learning activities in those social milieus in which solutions for housing problems are needed (integration, immigration) thus activating knowledge through interaction with society.	x
Enhancing interdisciplinarity and transdisciplinarity , by creating new learning spaces which bring together different disciplines into the solution of housing problems.	x
Contributing to the development of technology enhanced learning , embedding ICT in the learning processes and learning structures.	x